

SONIC-O1: A Real-World Benchmark for Evaluating Multimodal Large Language Models on Audio-Video Understanding

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Abstract

Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs) are a major focus of recent AI research. However, most prior work focuses on static image understanding, while their ability to process sequential audio–video data remains underexplored. This gap highlights the need for a high-quality benchmark to systematically evaluate MLLM performance in a real-world setting. We introduce **SONIC-O1**, a comprehensive, fully human-verified benchmark spanning 13 real-world conversational domains with 4,958 annotations and demographic metadata. SONIC-O1 evaluates MLLMs on key tasks, including open-ended summarization, multiple-choice question (MCQ) answering, and temporal localization with supporting rationales (reasoning). Experiments on closed- and open-source models reveal limitations. While the performance gap in MCQ accuracy between two model families is relatively small, we observe a substantial **22.6%** performance difference in temporal localization between the best performing closed-source and open-source models. Performance further degrades across demographic groups, indicating persistent disparities in model behavior. Overall, SONIC-O1 provides an open evaluation suite for temporally grounded and socially robust multimodal understanding. We release SONIC-O1 for reproducibility and research:

[Project page](#) [Dataset](#) [Github](#)
[Leaderboard](#)

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Figure 1. Performance comparison across 13 conversational domains. We compare closed-source and open-source MLLMs across 13 conversational domains using LLM-judge scores (0–10) for video summarization task. Gemini 3.0 Pro consistently outperforms open-source models, and high-stakes domains (e.g., Emergency Response, Mental Health) remain more challenging.

1. Introduction

MLLMs have advanced from static image captioning to general-purpose perception-and-reasoning systems capable of processing video and audio inputs (Fu et al., 2024b). These models are increasingly deployed to assist real-world decisions through conversational interactions. As MLLMs move into high-stakes such as healthcare, education, and public safety capability alone is insufficient. We must also evaluate whether these systems behave *accurately, fairly across demographics*, and *transparently* across diverse users and situations.

Real-world interactions rely fundamentally on both audio and video modalities. For example, speech conveys affect, emphasis, hesitation, and social intent that are essential for understanding communication. However, existing audio-video benchmarks exhibit two critical gaps. First, audio is frequently treated as optional or replaced with transcripts and subtitles (Ataallah et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2025),

Figure 2. Overview of SONIC-O1 tasks and evaluation format: **(Top)** video summarization, **(Middle)** evidence-grounded MCQ, **(Bottom)** temporal localization (event timing). Each example shows the input clip (frames) and the expected output format; demographic attributes shown beneath each clip represent associated metadata, enabling group-wise evaluation across 13 domains.

under-exploring paralinguistic cues that shape interpretation of speaker meaning and their emotional state. Second, even when native audio-video inputs are evaluated, group-wise analysis across demographic groups remains largely absent (Chen et al., 2024; Li et al., 2025a), precluding assessment of whether model performance varies systematically with user characteristics. Together, these limitations obscure whether current MLLMs can operate accurately and fairly in real-world deployment scenarios. We present a comparison of seminal audio-video benchmarks in Table 1.

To this end, we introduce **SONIC-O1**, a **S**ocial **N**atural **I**nteraction **C**orpus (**O**mnimodal, **v1**), the first open-source, fully human-verified benchmark of **4,958** audio-video question-answer (QA) instances derived from ≈ 60 hours of real-world audio-video interactions. As shown in Figure 3, the dataset spans 13 high-impact topics across 5 domains (including legal/civic, educational, and public health), covering real-world scenarios. SONIC-O1 covers videos that range from 30 seconds to 60 minutes (covering both short, medium, long duration) and tagged with metadata covering 6 racial groups, genders, and age groups.

SONIC-O1 evaluates three important evaluation tasks on state-of-the-art MLLMs: (i) **summarization** for global comprehension, (ii) **multiple-choice QA** for fine-grained reasoning, and (iii) **temporal localization** for identifying when events occur. Unlike prior work that treats audio as op-

tional (as shown in Table 1), SONIC-O1 requires native audio-video reasoning in an omnimodal (audio, video, and text) setting, where models use the audio-video input together with text to evaluate MLLMs' responses. Our goal with this work is to reveal where omnimodal MLLMs succeed, fail, and diverge across demographic groups in conversational contexts.

Contributions. (1) We introduce SONIC-O1, an open-source benchmark with human-verified domain-expert annotations and demographic metadata for evaluating MLLM performance and group-wise analysis on real-world interactions. (2) We benchmark omnimodal MLLMs, revealing substantial performance gaps and systematic disparities across demographic groups. (3) We release the full evaluation suite (dataset, scripts, leaderboard) under a research license.

Our evaluation reveals several key findings. (1) Closed-source models consistently outperform open-source alternatives, (2) temporal localization remains the most challenging task, and (3) systematic demographic disparities persist across models.

2. Related Work

Growth in MLLMs. MLLMs have rapidly evolved from static image understanding (Radford et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022) to video comprehension (Sun et al., 2019; Tong et al.,

Table 1. Comparison of video-QA benchmarks. SONIC-O1 uniquely combines comprehensive temporal understanding, audio-visual reasoning, social cue analysis, and open-source availability with both automatic and human annotations across diverse video lengths. **Legend:** ✓ = Yes, ✗ = No, δ = Partial temporal, AVQA = Audio-Visual Question Answering, MCQs = Multiple Choice Questions.

Benchmark	Data Size	Video Lengths (min)	QA Type	Summ.	Temp. [†]	Reas. [‡]	AVQA	Social [*] Cues	Annotation		Open Src
									Auto	Human	
<i>Video-QA Benchmarks (AVQA: ✗)</i>											
Video-MME (Fu et al., 2025)	2,700	<2; 4–15; 30–60	MCQs	✗	δ	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
LongVideoBench (Wu et al., 2024)	6,678	~8	MCQs	✗	δ	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
LVBench (Wang et al., 2025)	1,549	~68	MCQs	✗	δ	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
CinePile (Rawal et al., 2024)	305K	~3	MCQs	✗	δ	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗
Sports-QA (Li et al., 2024b)	94,000	<1	Open-ended	✗	δ	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗
InfiniBench (Ataallah et al., 2025)	87,700	~53	MCQs + Open	✓	δ	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
<i>Audio-Visual Benchmarks (AVQA: ✓)</i>											
VAST (Chen et al., 2023)	27M	<1	Captioning	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
Daily-Omni (Zhou et al., 2025b)	1,197	<1	MCQs	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
MAVERIX (Xie et al., 2025)	2,556	~6	MCQs + Open	✗	δ	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
CG-Bench (Chen et al., 2024)	12,129	10–60	MCQs + Open	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
OmniVideoBench (Li et al., 2025a)	1,000	1–30	MCQs + Open	✓	δ	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
AURA (Galougah et al., 2025)	1,600	<1	MCQs	✗	δ	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
SONIC-O1	4,958	<5; 5–20; 20–60	MCQs + Open	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

^{*}Social Cues: Demographic metadata (race, gender, age) annotated from observable characteristics in videos via AI-assisted human review (see Appendix A.7), enabling fairness evaluation across demographic groups. [†]Temporal: Temporal localization questions requiring localizing start and end of an event. [‡]Reasoning: Open-ended explanation of the given answer from the model.

2022). Recent vision-language models (Bai et al., 2023; Li et al., 2024a; Maaz et al., 2024) extend these capabilities to video, but they often operate over sampled frames and text, treating audio as auxiliary rather than integral to multimodal reasoning. In contrast, a new generation of *omnimodal* MLLMs, including VITA 1.5 (Fu et al., 2024a), Qwen3-Omni (Xu et al., 2025), Gemini 3.0 Pro (DeepMind, 2025), MiniCPM-o-2.6 (Yao et al., 2024), and UniMoE-2.0 (Li et al., 2025b), jointly process audio, video, and text within a unified framework. Omnimodal MLLMs thus refer to models designed for integrated reasoning across multiple modalities (Jiang et al., 2025). However, evaluation benchmarks have not kept pace. Existing datasets often omit audio entirely, replace it with text transcripts, or lack the demographic annotations necessary to assess group-wise performance across diverse user populations.

Video Benchmarks. Recent benchmarks have begun to evaluate temporal reasoning across diverse video lengths, including short-form tasks such as MVBench (Li et al., 2025a) and TempCompass (Liu et al., 2024), as well as long-form understanding in Video-MME (Fu et al., 2025) (up to one hour) and LongVideoBench (Wu et al., 2024). However, two critical gaps remain. First, **audio is underutilized**. Even when available, evaluations often default to frame- or subtitle-based setups due to limited model support. Second, **group-wise analysis is largely absent**, preventing systematic measurement of performance disparities across demographic groups. As shown in Table 1, SONIC-O1 addresses these limitations by combining native audio-video evaluation, temporal localization, and demographic metadata to enable group-wise analysis assessment.

3. SONIC-O1: Dataset and Benchmark Design

In this section, we describe the design of the SONIC-O1 dataset and benchmark.

3.1. Data Collection

The construction of SONIC-O1 is grounded in real-world data. To ensure broad coverage, we collected videos from YouTube (Google Developers, 2025) restricted to CC BY 4.0 licenses. We target five high-stakes domains, such as *Professional, Educational, Legal/Civic, Service-Oriented, and Public Health*, subdivided into 13 topics (e.g., job interviews, courtroom proceedings) as shown in Figure 3. To benchmark long-context capabilities, we stratified sampling across three duration ranges: short (<5 minutes), medium (5–20 minutes), and long (20–60 minutes). Our search strategy combined topic keywords with demographic descriptors (race, gender, age) to maximize representation. From an initial pool of 2,237 candidates, 1,794 met licensing constraints, and subsequent manual quality filtering yielded 231 final videos totaling approximately 60 hours. SONIC-O1 provides fully human-verified, real-world audio-video content in sensitive domains with perceived demographic annotations, enabling fairness-oriented slice analysis that is typically not reported in movie/TV-based benchmarks (Song et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2025) or in many judge-based / synthetically-evaluated evaluation suites (Fang et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2025a). Full details are provided in Appendix A.

3.2. Tasks Annotation

We define three evaluation tasks over the same video pool and discuss them below. Figure 4b shows the annotation

Figure 3. Video categories. Our benchmark covers 5 key domains and 13 video topics.

counts per task across the 13 topics; Appendix A.7 describes the AI-assisted annotation workflow and prompts.

Table 2. SONIC-O1 task statistics.

Task	#Inst.	Unit / Ground Truth
Summarization	231	Full video \rightarrow reference summary
MCQ	1,335	3-minutes overlap video segment \rightarrow answer + reasoning
Temporal loc.	3,392	3-minutes overlap video segment \rightarrow relation + (t_s, t_e) + reasoning
Total	4,958	231 videos (\approx 60 hours)

Task 1: Video Summarization. This task requires models to summarize videos by capturing key events, actions, and outcomes. Following established video summarization benchmarks (Ning et al., 2025), models generate a detailed narrative summary up to 300 words. During annotation, to preserve coverage for long videos, we apply a hierarchical procedure, where videos longer than 10 minutes are segmented into 10-minute chunks to context limits, each chunk is summarized, and the chunk-level summaries are merged into a final reference summary. The task contains 231 summarization instances, each consisting of an audio-video input paired with a human-verified reference summary.

Task 2: MCQs with Reasoning. This task evaluates fine-grained understanding of local video segments using a controlled answer space, a common design for objective comparison in video benchmarks (Ye et al., 2024; Lei et al., 2018; Patraucean et al., 2023). We operate on segments of up to 3 minutes; longer videos are split into 3-minute

(a) Video duration distribution over topics

(b) Question type distribution over topics

Figure 4. Video duration and question type distributions. SONIC-O1 spans a full spectrum of video lengths and evaluates core abilities of MLLMs.

windows with 30-second overlap. For each segment, we construct an MCQ with five choices, consisting of four candidate answers plus a *Not enough evidence* option. During evaluation, MLLMs must choose the correct answer and provide a rationale grounded in visual and auditory evidence.

Task 3: Temporal Localization. This task evaluates temporal reasoning by grounding events with timestamps (e.g., whether a diagnosis occurs before or after symptoms). Temporal localization is standard in audio-video benchmarks for fine-grained event alignment (Zhou et al., 2025b; Geng et al., 2025). We extend this by requiring models to predict timestamps and provide rationales grounded in audio-visual evidence. We use an anchor-target formulation that given an anchor event, models must (1) predict the target’s start and end times, and (2) provide a reasoning with salient evidence. Domain experts label times relative to each segment’s start (0.0s), which are converted to absolute timestamps by adding the segment’s offset. The dataset contains 3,392 instances (up to three per segment), each with target timestamps and supporting reasoning.

3.3. Quality Assurance

Each evaluation task is manually reviewed and verified by domain experts; team details and guidelines are provided in Appendix B.1. Experts watched each full video before labeling, with the ability to revisit any timestamp as needed.

Table 3. Performance of MLLMs on SONIC-O1. We report results on all dataset across three tasks: summarization (LLM-judge score, Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation–L (ROUGE-L), cosine similarity), multiple-choice questions (MCQs; accuracy and rationale quality), and temporal localization (mean Intersection-over-Union (mIoU), Recall@0.5 (R@0.5), and rationale quality). Accuracy, mIoU, R@0.5, and ROUGE-L are reported as percentages; cosine similarity is in [0,1]. All metrics are macro-averaged across all topics in the benchmark. Frames per video (FPV) and frames per second (FPS) denote input settings. Higher is better. **Bold** denotes best performance, underline denotes second-best per task-metric. † represents closed-source model. Detailed results in Appendix A4.

Model	LLM Params	Summarization			MCQ				Temporal Localization				
		Score	ROUGE-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim	mIoU	R@0.5	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim
Gemini 3.0 Pro † (1 FPS)	-	7.07	27.2	0.81	96.4	9.38	36.9	0.80	26.6	25.4	5.38	28.3	<u>0.67</u>
Qwen3-Omni (256 FPV)	30B	<u>5.72</u>	<u>22.8</u>	<u>0.71</u>	<u>93.6</u>	<u>8.88</u>	<u>33.8</u>	<u>0.78</u>	<u>3.7</u>	<u>2.8</u>	2.58	<u>28.0</u>	0.70
UniMoE-2.0 (256 FPV)	33B	4.71	20.8	0.70	88.2	8.12	26.5	0.73	1.8	1.0	2.11	23.7	0.55
MiniCPM-o-2.6 (256 FPV)	9B	3.34	14.7	0.56	87.4	8.01	24.4	0.73	1.8	0.7	3.65	19.3	0.41
VITA 1.5 (64 FPV)	8B	2.77	16.3	0.49	81.5	7.72	25.2	0.71	1.8	1.2	<u>3.91</u>	22.1	0.43
VideoLLaMA 2 (128 FPV)	7B	1.53	12.7	0.38	54.3	5.11	18.9	0.58	3.5	0.4	2.22	22.5	0.49

To support scalable annotation, we used Gemini 2.5 Flash to draft perceived demographic metadata (race, gender, age) and task annotations across all tasks, inspired by prior benchmark efforts (Ataallah et al., 2025). Full prompts are given in Appendix A.7.1. All outputs were then verified, corrected, and revised via our internal review interface (Appendix B.3). We removed any items with ambiguity, insufficient evidence, or annotation errors and resolved disagreements through consensus adjudication. This process results in the construction of SONIC-O1, with dataset statistics reported in Table 2 and further details provided in Appendix C.

3.4. Evaluation Suite

We release a full evaluation suite. While existing audio–video benchmarks (Table 1) often provide limited datasets and evaluation scripts, they are not always designed to scale as new MLLMs, interaction formats, and task variants emerge. To address this, we release an extensible SONIC-O1 evaluation suite that offers a unified framework for models operating on direct audio–video inputs, with consistent segmenting and sampling policies for long videos. The suite modularizes the pipeline into data loading, inference, and metric computation, supporting both commercial and open-source MLLMs across heterogeneous API formats. This design lowers the barrier to adoption and provides a practical foundation for reproducible evaluation and future community extensions.

4. Experiments

In this section, we define our experimental setup.

4.1. Settings

Evaluated model suite We conduct the evaluation on commercial and open-source MLLMs. For commercial models, we used Gemini-3.0-Pro (DeepMind, 2025) and GPT-4o (OpenAI, 2024) (ablation only). Representative

open-source omni MLLMs including Qwen3-Omni-30B-A3B (Xu et al., 2025), Uni-MoE-2.0-Omni (Li et al., 2025b), MiniCPM-o-2.6 (Yao et al., 2024), VITA-1.5 (Fu et al., 2024a), and VideoLLaMA2 (Cheng et al., 2024) are evaluated as well. We prioritize those models that natively support audio-video inputs. GPT-4o supports vision-text but not native audio, so we include it for modality ablation. We follow best configurations and practices for open-source MLLMs, setting maximum frames at 256 with adaptive fallback for models with context limitation. Model details and settings appear in Table A3 and Appendix D

Metrics We employ both statistical and LLM-based metrics, following evaluation protocols as in related works (Fang et al., 2024; Ataallah et al., 2025). For summarization, we report ROUGE-L, cosine similarity, and an LLM judge score (GPT-5-mini with 0–10 scale). For MCQs, we report accuracy (%); we additionally report the LLM judge score on open-ended reasoning for this task. For temporal localization, we report mean intersection over union (mIoU) and recall at intersection over union (R@0.5). Full definitions and prompts are in Appendix E.

4.2. Results and Analysis

In this section, we report the performance of MLLMs on SONIC-O1.

Performance of MLLMs models on SONIC-O1. We report comprehensive evaluation results across all three tasks in Table 3. Overall, we observe that the closed-source model Gemini 3.0 Pro achieves the highest performance among all models, obtaining 96.4% MCQ accuracy, a 7.07 judge score on summarization, and 25.4% R@0.5 on temporal localization. In the temporal localization task, we observe a large performance gap of about 23% between Gemini 3.0 and the next-best open-source Qwen3-Omni model.

Among open-source models, Qwen3-Omni demonstrates the strongest overall performance, achieving 93.6% MCQ

accuracy and 5.72 judge score on summarization. UniMoE-2.0 attains 88.2% MCQ accuracy, but its summarization capabilities remain weaker (4.71 judge score). The results further show that model scale plays a key role, with smaller models showing some performance limitations. MiniCPM-o-2.6 and VideoLLaMA2 are built on smaller Qwen backbones. They show noticeable drops compared to Qwen3-Omni (30B), with a 41.6% lower judge score on summarization, 6.62% lower MCQ accuracy, and 51.4% lower R@0.5 on temporal localization.

Key Finding: Closed-source models remain consistently ahead, with temporal localization is the most challenging task for current open-source models. The summarization and MCQ tasks are relatively easier for MLLMs. Larger open-source models provide measurable gains, however, they do not fully close the performance gap.

Table 4. Performance of MLLMs on summarization task across demographic groups. Results are on all dataset reported using LLM judge Score (0–10), higher scores indicate better performance. **Bold:** best, **highlighted:** worst within each group per column. Detailed results in Appendix Table A15

Group	Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	Qwen3 Omni	UniMoE 2.0	MiniCPM o-2.6	VITA 1.5	Video LLaMA2
<i>Race</i>						
Arab	6.90	5.95	5.00	3.57	2.76	1.00
Indigenous	6.70	4.13	4.35	3.61	1.65	1.04
Asian	7.05	5.71	4.62	3.26	2.65	1.63
White	6.68	5.28	4.29	3.26	2.50	1.45
Hispanic	6.41	4.99	3.70	3.04	2.21	1.23
Black	6.02	4.39	3.45	2.92	2.31	1.38
<i>Gender</i>						
Male	6.36	4.97	3.93	2.98	2.31	1.36
Female	7.02	5.47	4.55	3.53	2.65	1.53
<i>Age</i>						
18–24	6.28	4.93	4.02	3.30	2.41	1.38
25–39	6.52	5.01	4.01	3.14	2.45	1.50
40+	6.91	5.47	4.45	3.21	2.47	1.36

Table 5. MCQ performance across demographic groups. Accuracy (%), with higher values indicating better performance. Detailed results in Appendix Table A16.

Group	Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	Qwen3 Omni	UniMoE 2.0	MiniCPM o-2.6	VITA 1.5	Video LLaMA2
<i>Race</i>						
Arab	98.4	96.9	95.3	92.7	93.2	67.0
Indigenous	94.3	77.1	80.0	82.9	62.9	65.7
Asian	97.8	96.1	89.2	88.7	84.6	58.1
White	96.9	93.3	89.0	87.6	82.3	55.0
Hispanic	95.8	92.8	86.4	82.2	79.9	51.5
Black	96.4	92.0	87.7	86.9	82.7	55.4
<i>Gender</i>						
Male	96.3	93.5	88.4	86.5	82.2	53.0
Female	97.6	93.4	89.3	88.3	83.8	60.0
<i>Age</i>						
18–24	97.4	91.5	83.3	84.5	83.0	54.8
25–39	95.6	92.7	87.7	86.8	81.7	55.8
40+	98.0	94.6	91.0	88.4	84.0	56.3

Performance across demographic groups. We report MLLM performance stratified by race, gender, and age in Tables 4, 5, and 6 to quantify demographic disparities.

Table 6. Temporal localization performance across demographic groups. Results are reported as R@0.5 (%), where higher values indicate better temporal grounding. Detailed results in Appendix Tables A17 and A18.

Group	Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	Qwen3 Omni	UniMoE 2.0	MiniCPM o-2.6	VITA 1.5	Video LLaMA2
<i>Race</i>						
Arab	21.1	1.6	0.2	2.6	1.2	0.0
Indigenous	40.9	0.0	1.3	0.0	1.3	1.3
Asian	30.7	2.9	0.6	0.8	1.4	0.4
White	23.0	2.6	1.2	0.9	1.4	0.5
Hispanic	23.8	2.3	0.1	0.2	0.8	0.0
Black	19.5	1.8	0.6	0.3	1.4	0.3
<i>Gender</i>						
Male	23.5	2.6	0.9	0.7	1.2	0.4
Female	24.2	2.1	0.7	0.9	1.4	0.4
<i>Age</i>						
18–24	27.3	2.4	1.2	1.1	1.1	0.3
25–39	25.2	2.5	1.2	0.7	1.2	0.3
40+	21.9	2.3	0.4	0.8	1.5	0.4

Overall, we observe that the closed-source Gemini 3.0 Pro achieves the strongest performance across nearly all demographic groups, while Qwen3-Omni is the most competitive open-source model. MCQ accuracy is relatively stable across groups, whereas summarization scores show larger variation. The largest gaps emerge in temporal localization (R@0.5), particularly across racial groups (e.g., Indigenous: 40.9% vs. Black: 19.5%). Race shows the most pronounced disparities, with smaller gender effects and generally higher performance for participants aged 40+. Female participants achieve slightly higher scores, one possible contributor is that safety alignment can shift response tone and refusal tendencies, which may interact with our scoring. Finally, smaller models appear less robust across demographic slices.

Key Finding: While aggregate results (Table 3) provide overall task rankings, however, group-wise demographic analysis reveals that temporal localization shows substantially larger disparities across race and age than averages suggest, while MCQ remains stable across groups.

Performance across topics. We also observe consistent topic-level variation. As can be seen in Figure 1 Gemini 3.0 Pro performs best across nearly all domains, Qwen3-Omni and UniMoE-2.0 (30B) form a competitive middle tier, while smaller 7-9B models drop sharply. High-stakes scenarios (e.g., emergency response, mental health) are most challenging to solve by MLLMs, whereas some topics in professional settings (e.g., consultations, interviews) are comparatively easier (Appendix G).

Key Finding: Robustness remains uneven across topics, with the largest gaps in emotionally sensitive contexts.

Performance across short, medium, and long durations. Table 7 reports MLLM performance stratified by video duration (short < 5 minutes, medium 5–20 minutes, long 20–

Table 7. **Duration robustness of MLLMs across video lengths.** Performance is reported on all dataset for short, medium, and long videos. Summarization is measured using LLM-judge scores, MCQ using accuracy (%), and temporal localization using R@0.5 (%). Higher values indicate better performance. **Bold** and underline denote the best and second-best results within each duration bin and task.

Model	LLM Params	Summarization (Score)			MCQ (Accuracy)			Temporal Localization (R@0.5)		
		Short	Medium	Long	Short	Medium	Long	Short	Medium	Long
Gemini 3.0 Pro	-	8.16	6.11	6.63	98.9	95.1	96.9	50.6	26.0	18.6
Qwen3-Omni	30B	6.64	4.95	4.87	91.5	93.6	<u>94.5</u>	<u>9.2</u>	<u>2.6</u>	<u>2.5</u>
UniMoE-2.0	33B	5.49	4.37	3.87	89.4	86.5	<u>90.9</u>	6.9	0.3	0.6
MiniCPM-o-2.6	9B	4.08	2.87	2.87	<u>92.6</u>	84.8	89.2	0.9	1.1	0.6
VITA 1.5	8B	3.39	2.40	2.46	<u>85.1</u>	78.4	82.4	3.0	1.2	1.0
VideoLLaMA 2	7B	1.89	1.46	1.27	61.7	55.5	52.7	0.9	0.3	0.4

Table 8. **Effect of input modalities.** Performance of representative MLLMs on representative topics under different input modalities (video-only vs. video+audio). Summarization is reported using LLM-judge scores (task-specific scale); MCQ is reported using accuracy (%) and rationale score; Temporal localization is reported using R@0.5 (%) and rationale score. Bold denotes the best within each model.

Model	Video	Audio	Sum. (Score)	MCQ (Acc./Score)	Temporal (R@0.5/Score)
Qwen3-Omni	✓ ✓	✗ ✓	4.60 6.82	86.1 / 7.98 96.8 / 9.42	1.6 / 2.55 4.2 / 2.69
UniMoE-2.0	✓ ✓	✗ ✓	3.96 5.86	83.9 / 8.09 92.7 / 8.89	0.7 / 2.42 1.2 / 2.06
VideoLLaMA2	✓ ✓	✗ ✓	2.02 1.88	54.6 / 5.61 57.1 / 5.23	0.8 / 2.89 0.6 / 2.13
GPT4o	✓ ✓	✗ ✓	5.02 5.82	91.2 / 8.83 97.5 / 9.41	4.3 / 2.87 3.0 / 2.93

Note: For GPT4o, the "Audio" column corresponds to *Text* input (i.e., GPT4o uses Video+Text instead of Video+Audio).

60 minutes) to assess the impact of temporal extent. Overall, we observe that Gemini 3.0 Pro consistently achieves the highest performance across all video lengths (short, medium, long) on all three tasks. Smaller models like VITA 1.5, VideoLLaMA2 shows limited robustness to longer and more complex videos. We also observe that performance degrades as video length increases, with temporal localization most affected, while MCQ remains relatively stable.

Key Finding: Performance declines on longer videos, with temporal localization most affected by the challenge of sustained event tracking.

4.3. Ablation studies

The impact of input modality and frame sampling rate is examined through ablation studies on three representative topics, including patient–doctor consultations (T1), job interviews (T2), and courtroom proceedings (T5).

Effect of input modalities. Table 8 presents a modality ablation study comparing video-only input (frames without audio) to combined video+audio input. The results show that adding audio improves performance across most models and tasks. For example, Qwen3-Omni improves from

86.1% to 96.8% MCQ accuracy and from a 4.60 to 6.82 summarization score when audio is added. GPT-4o (using text transcripts instead of native audio) gains 6.3% in MCQ accuracy with text modality. However, the magnitude of improvement varies by model and task. Qwen3-Omni benefits most consistently, with adding audio yielding +10.7% MCQ accuracy, +2.22 summarization score, and +2.6% R@0.5 in temporal localization. Smaller models show weaker gains, e.g., VideoLLaMA2 exhibits mixed results, with slight degradation in summarization (-0.14 score) despite small MCQ gains (+2.5%).

Key Finding: Multimodal inputs improve performance across tasks, with larger models benefiting more consistently than smaller models, suggesting effective audio-visual fusion requires sufficient model capacity.

Effect of frame sampling rate. MLLMs typically operate over a limited set of uniformly sampled frames (e.g., 16 or 32), raising the question of whether denser visual coverage improves performance. Figure 5 shows that increasing the number of input frames does not consistently yield gains. For summarization and MCQ (Figures 5a and 5b), accuracy remains largely unchanged, suggesting that additional frames provide limited benefit for high-level semantic understanding. In contrast, temporal localization (Figure 5c) improves more noticeably with higher frame counts for stronger models (e.g., Qwen3-Omni), while weaker models (e.g., VideoLLaMA2) exhibit inconsistent trends.

Key Finding: Higher frames primarily benefit temporal localization, but yield little gain for summarization or MCQ.

4.4. Qualitative Analysis

To characterize the baseline emotional language profiles of different models, we analyze generated audio-video empathic summaries using linguistic inquiry and word count (LIWC-22), a validated dictionary-based tool (Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010; Boyd et al., 2022) (details in Appendix J). We examine total emotional expression, negative emotion, and overall tone, which capture differences in affective style and warmth in unconstrained model outputs. Results in Table 9 reveal distinct default emotional profiles

Figure 5. **Frame-count sensitivity across metrics.** Performance of three representative MLLMs (Qwen3-Omni, UniMoE-2, VideoLLaMA2) on representative topics across varying frame counts (16, 32, 64, 128) for three tasks: (a) Summarization quality measured by LLM judge scores, (b) Multiple-choice question accuracy, and (c) Temporal localization R@0.5. Models exhibit different saturation patterns across tasks.

Table 9. **Emotional language analysis.** Analysis of MLLM empathic summary outputs on the all dataset (Task 1: summarization). Total Emotion (%) denotes the percentage of words expressing any emotion; Neg. Emotion (%) denotes the percentage of words expressing negative affect; Tone reflects overall warmth and positivity (higher values indicate a warmer, more informal tone). **Bold** denotes best performance and **highlighted** denotes worst.

Model	Total Emotion (%)	Neg. Emotion (%)	Tone
Gemini 3.0 Pro	4.35	2.03	46.16
Qwen3-Omni	3.88	1.39	56.99
UniMoE-2.0	3.54	0.93	57.94
MiniCPM-o-2.6	1.41	0.38	46.10
VITA-1.5	2.65	0.59	55.45
VideoLLaMA2	2.02	0.49	49.83

across MLLMs. Gemini 3.0 Pro adopts a neutral, clinical style with higher emotional acknowledgment but lower tone scores. In contrast, Qwen3-Omni and UniMoE-2.0 exhibit a warmer, more supportive profile, characterized by higher tone scores and reduced negative emotion. Smaller models (e.g., MiniCPM-o-2.6, VideoLLaMA2) show limited emotional modulation, indicating reduced capacity for affective language adjustment.

Key Finding: MLLMs demonstrate distinct baseline emotional language styles, with larger models showing richer affective expression. These profiles reflect default tendencies rather than controlled emotional modulation capabilities.

5. Discussion and Limitations

Our results reveal a clear gap in current MLLMs. They excel at content understanding but struggle with temporal grounding. Video inputs offer limited gains, and temporal localization remains especially challenging for open-source models. Frequent hallucinated time references point to deeper weaknesses in internal temporal reasoning.

Limitations. We acknowledge some limitations of this study. SONIC-O1 focuses on English-language interactions,

which may limit cultural and linguistic coverage. Although annotations are human-verified, some subjectivity remains, particularly for open-ended tasks. The benchmark is also restricted in scale and task scope, and findings may not fully generalize to other domains, modalities, or future model generations.

From an **evaluation perspective**, some constraints are observed. First, many MLLMs rely on similar Qwen-based backbones but we observe that they differ substantially in audio processing. In practice, long audio streams are often truncated to fixed durations rather than adaptively aligned with sampled video frames. Second, models frequently struggle with absolute temporal localization. When clips do not begin at zero (e.g., 500–800s), predictions are often reported relative to the segment start (e.g., 50–80s instead of 550–580s), suggesting reliance on relative playback position rather than robust temporal representations (see error taxonomy in Appendix H). Third, demographic groups have unequal sample sizes (Figure A7), which may increase variance for underrepresented groups. Finally, context-length limitations require video segmentation for most models, which can further amplify temporal errors. In contrast, Gemini’s larger context window allows processing full videos at 1 FPS, reducing the need for segmentation.

6. Conclusion

We introduced **SONIC-O1**, a real-world audio-video benchmark for evaluating MLLMs performance through the lens of perceived demographic fairness. SONIC-O1 includes human-verified annotations and three tasks. These are summarization, MCQs, and temporal localization with reasonings, to assess both semantic understanding and temporal grounding. Our findings show that audio or transcripts often provide the strongest cues for comprehension, while temporal localization remains the most challenging setting. We also observe persistent demographic disparities across mod-

els, emphasizing the need for more equitable multimodal evaluation. Overall, SONIC-O1 offers a practical testbed for evaluating MLLMs in realistic audio-video scenarios, and we hope it will guide future work on stronger temporal reasoning and broader benchmark coverage.

Impact Statement

SONIC-O1 is designed to support the responsible development of audio–video models. It is intended to help researchers, practitioners, and organizations better understand how these systems behave, especially in sensitive areas such as media analysis, education, and public information. Like other public benchmarks, the results could be taken out of context or selectively used in adversarial, reputational, or legal situations if the limitations are ignored. While SONIC-O1 examines gaps affecting marginalized demographic groups, this analysis is meant to identify and reduce potential harms, not to reinforce stereotypes, offend communities, or be used against any group.

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A. Data Collection Details

As illustrated in the *Retrieval & Metadata* stage of Figure A1, we retrieve real-world scenario videos using the YouTube Data API v3 (Google Developers, 2025), following established ethical frameworks for web-based data collection that respect contextual integrity and avoid privacy violations (Zimmer, 2020; Nissenbaum, 2004). We restrict candidates to videos published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) license (Creative Commons, 2013), which explicitly permits redistribution for research purposes. Videos under YouTube’s Standard License are excluded due to redistribution restrictions.

Our search strategy uses topic-specific base queries that capture real-world interactions (e.g., consultations, interviews, hearings), and expands them with demographic descriptors (e.g., “young adult”, “woman”, “Black”, “Middle Eastern”, “First Nations”), following federal standards for demographic categorization (U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission, 2006), to improve coverage. These demographic keywords are used only for query expansion and are not treated as labels; final demographic annotations are produced later through a human-verified review process (Appendix A.7). This approach ensures that our data collection respects the original context and licensing terms under which content was shared (Zimmer, 2020), avoiding privacy violations that can occur when data is extracted from contexts with restricted access expectations.

Figure A1. **SONIC-O1 data curation and annotation pipeline.** We first retrieve candidate real-world scenario videos via topic- and demographic-augmented search queries and filter by licensing constraints (CC BY 4.0), then download video/audio and any available captions. Human reviewers screen candidates for quality and coverage, after which we parse metadata and perform balanced sampling (e.g., by topic and duration). For benchmark construction, videos are segmented into 10-minute chunks for summarization (T1) and into overlapping 3-minute segments for MCQ and temporal localization (T2–T3). If captions are unavailable, we obtain speech transcripts via ASR; otherwise we use downloaded captions. Draft demographic metadata and task annotations can be bootstrapped with model-assisted tools (e.g., Gemini/ASR) and are subsequently corrected and verified by domain experts, with ambiguous or low-evidence items removed. Arrows indicate the flow from raw retrieval to finalized, human-verified instances.

A.1. Curation Strategy and Licensing Compliance

To construct SONIC-O1, we followed a structured video curation pipeline combining keyword-based API retrieval with strict license filtering. We restricted candidates to CC BY 4.0 videos and performed additional manual verification to ensure redistribution and research-use compliance.

Example Search Query Construction (4 of 13 Topics Shown)**Base Query Examples Across Topics:***Topic 2: Job Interviews (Professional Domain)*

- panel interview full interview
- technical interview session full
- candidate interview recording

Topic 1: Patient-Doctor Consultations (Community/Public Health)

- doctor patient conversation full session
- clinic consultation recording
- telehealth visit recording

Topic 5: Courtroom Proceedings (Legal/Civic)

- oral argument
- sentencing hearing full recording courtroom
- small claims court full hearing official recording

Topic 7: Public Transportation Conflicts (Community/Public Health)

- bus passenger fight driver -news -compilation
- train passenger confrontation cctv
- airport security passenger meltdown bodycam

Demographic Variations Generated (Example: Job Interviews):

- **Race:** Black panel interview full interview, Asian technical interview session full, Hispanic candidate interview recording, Middle Eastern panel interview full interview, White technical interview session full
- **Gender:** woman panel interview full interview, man technical interview session full
- **Age:** young adult panel interview full interview, middle aged technical interview session full, older adult candidate interview recording

Special Handling for Underrepresented Groups:

- **Arab:** Multiple variations used: Arab, Middle Eastern, Arabic, MENA, Arab American
- **Indigenous:** Multiple variations used: Indigenous, Native American, First Nations, Aboriginal, tribal

This approach generated approximately 40–50 search queries per topic (4–6 base queries × 11 demographic variations), yielding diverse representation across racial, gender, and age groups. Total queries across 13 topics: ~600 searches.

A.2. Inclusion Criteria

Candidate videos must satisfy the following requirements:

- **Time of curation:** Only videos published from January 2020 to October 2025 to ensure topical coverage, availability, and consistency in retrieval conditions.
- **Keywords:** Topic-specific base queries that capture authentic, real-world interactions, further expanded with demographic descriptors for race, gender, and age.
- **Video lengths:** Recordings sufficient to capture complete interactions, typically ranging from 30 seconds-60 minutes.
- **Language:** Primarily English-language recordings with clear, intelligible speech to support multimodal transcription and reasoning tasks.
- **Topics & categories:** Videos covering 13 topics across five domains, selected to reflect common, high-impact real-world interactions relevant for multimodal reasoning.
- **Demographic diversity:** Videos featuring speakers across diverse **race** (White, Black, Asian, Indigenous, Arab, Hispanic), **gender** (male, female), and **age** groups (18–24, 25–39, 40+), following federal standards for demographic categorization (U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission, 2006; b;a).

A.3. Exclusion Criteria

Our upstream retrieval produces many candidates that are off-topic, low quality, or unsuitable for ethical/legal use. We therefore apply a two-stage filtering procedure: (i) lightweight metadata-only heuristics to remove obvious spam and outliers, followed by (ii) a **domain-expert human screening pass** (Figure A2) in which candidates are manually viewed and labeled as *Good* or *Bad*. We retain only videos labeled *Good* and licensed under **CC BY 4.0**.

A video is rejected if it meets any of the following criteria:

- **Low media quality:** poor audio or visual quality that hinders transcription, comprehension, or annotation.
- **Non-continuous content:** heavily edited or montage-style videos that do not preserve continuous interactions.
- **Irrelevant topic:** content not aligned with the target domains or study scope.
- **Sensitive or unsafe content:** videos containing sensitive personal data or content that cannot be used in an ethical manner.
- **Language constraint:** non-English, audio-dominant content that prevents reliable English annotation.
- **License constraint:** videos under YouTube’s Standard License (i.e., not CC BY 4.0).

A.4. Filtering and Media Processing

Stage 1: Metadata-only pre-filtering. Before human review, we apply lightweight heuristics using only public metadata to remove obviously low-quality uploads while preserving licensing and safety constraints. We drop candidates with missing basic signals (e.g., missing duration), enforce a duration window, and require a minimum view count (500 by default; 100 for scarce topics such as emergency response). We further filter clickbait/spam via simple title-based signals (e.g., excessive capitalization with caps ratio > 0.55 , heavy punctuation/repetition, emoji spam with > 5 emojis, and common spam phrases), suspicious engagement (e.g., $> 10k$ views with 0 likes and 0 comments, or $> 5k$ views with engagement rate $< 10^{-4}$), and invalid channels (e.g., extremely short or numeric-only channel identifiers). Remaining candidates receive a simple metadata quality score that rewards suitable durations and healthy engagement and penalizes generic/clickbait titles.

Stage 2: Human Review & Selection. During *Human Review & Selection* (Figure A1), reviewers label each candidate video as *Good* or *Bad* based on topic relevance, audio–visual quality, safety, and licensing.

Balanced sampling and media pre-processing. From the human-accepted pool, we construct the final set using a topic-capped, a balanced sampling procedure designed to maximize coverage under licensing and quality constraints. Concretely, we cap each topic at up to 25 videos when sufficient candidates exist and stratify selections across short, medium, and long durations to avoid over-representing any single length regime. When a topic contains fewer than the target after filtering, we include all eligible videos for that topic (i.e., no downsampling).

For each selected video, we download the MP4 (capped at 1080p to balance quality and storage), extract stereo audio (48 kHz, 192 kbps), and retrieve English captions via the YouTube caption API when available. Videos without native captions are flagged for automatic transcription. The output is a three-modality package per video—video (MP4), audio (M4A), and text (SRT)—plus a JSON metadata record containing IDs, timestamps, and processing artifacts for reproducibility.

A.5. Video Filtering Summary

Table A1 documents the filtering process from initial search to final dataset.

Table A1. **Video filtering summary.** Counts of candidate videos at each curation stage: initial API retrieval during time 2020-2025, CC BY 4.0 license filtering, and final acceptance after metadata pre-filtering and human *Good/Bad* screening. The sharp reduction reflects deliberate prioritization of licensing compliance, annotation quality, and balanced coverage over scale

Stage	Count
Initial search results	2,237
After license filtering (CC BY 4.0 only)	1,794
Final dataset (post quality assurance)	231

A.6. Topical Coverage

Table A2 summarizes SONIC-O1’s topical coverage across five conversational domains and 13 topics, including video counts and duration statistics for the curated set.

Table A2. **Topical coverage of SONIC-O1.** Breakdown of the 5 domains and 13 topics, reporting the number of curated videos (Samples) and their aggregate/average durations after the full selection pipeline.

Category	Topics	Samples	Total Duration (min)	Avg Duration (min)
Professional	Job interviews; workplace meetings	49	708.8	14.5
Educational	Parent–teacher conferences	18	651.5	36.2
Legal / Civic	Courtroom proceedings; community town halls	32	843.8	26.4
Service-Oriented	Customer service; restaurant service; housing/apartment tours	63	726.3	11.3
Community / Public Health	Medical (patient–doctor); emergency response; public transportation conflicts; mental-health counseling; Olympics/sports	69	681.2	9.7

A.7. AI-Assisted Annotation Process

Model-assisted drafting. In the *Demographics Annotation* and *Question Generation* stages (Figure A1), we use Gemini 2.5 Flash to produce **initial** drafts from joint multimodal signals (video, audio, and captions), where captions are always available (downloaded captions when present, otherwise generated via automatic speech recognition (ASR) using Whisper (Bain et al., 2023)). This approach follows established practices in recent benchmarking efforts (Galougah et al., 2025; Ataallah et al., 2025). Importantly, all drafts are then reviewed and corrected by domain expert annotators (Appendix B.1) using our review interface (Appendix B.3). Only human-verified annotations are retained for dataset construction and benchmarking.

Demographic annotation workflow. We first draft demographics at the **video level** as a set of tags (e.g., race, gender, age, language) using Gemini 2.5 Flash, and annotators review and correct these tags. During audio-video question-answering (AVQA) instance construction, we **propagate** the verified video-level tags to each segment by expanding them into per-segment counts of unique individuals per demographic combination. This expansion step is model-assisted but constrained

to the human-verified tag set (i.e., it cannot introduce new demographic values), and is again reviewed and corrected by the domain expert annotators. For each segment, we store human-verified demographic tags, optional confidence scores, and per-segment counts. For multi-person segments, we store counts of individuals grouped by unique demographic combinations (e.g., "2 White males aged 40+, 1 Asian female aged 25-39").

Task-specific annotation workflow. For all three tasks (summarization, MCQ, temporal localization), we use Gemini 2.5 Flash to draft questions, answers, and task-specific annotations. All model outputs undergo mandatory human verification, correction, and revision. The full prompts are provided in Appendix A.7.1.

Annotation schema. Each item includes the question or summary and a reference answer; for Tasks 2–3, we additionally store a short reasoning rationale. Each segment also includes human-verified demographic metadata (and optional confidence scores) with counts for each unique demographic combination when multiple individuals appear.

A.7.1. AI GENERATION PROMPTS

Below are the complete prompts used to generate preliminary annotation drafts for each task and the initial demographics prompt. All AI-generated outputs underwent mandatory human verification as described in Section A.8.

Demographic Generation Prompt.

Demographics: AI Annotation Generation

You are a demographics annotation specialist for academic research. Analyze the provided multimodal media (video, audio, and captions/transcripts) and identify the demographic characteristics of all individuals who appear visually or speak. Be objective and avoid stereotype-based assumptions. Return ONLY valid JSON that can be directly parsed (no extra text).

Analyze this MULTIMODAL media to identify demographics of ALL people who appear visually or speak.

MEDIA INFORMATION:

- Title: {title}
- Duration: {duration_seconds} seconds
- Topic: {topic_name}

INPUTS PROVIDED:

You have access to multiple modalities for this analysis:

1. VIDEO: Visual content showing individuals (if available)
2. AUDIO: Sound/speech from individuals (may be embedded in video or separate)
3. TRANSCRIPT/CAPTIONS: Text representation of spoken content
{transcript_preview}

IMPORTANT: Use ALL available modalities together for the most accurate analysis. Cross-reference visual, audio, and text cues to identify and confirm demographics.

ANALYSIS GUIDELINES BY MODALITY:

VIDEO ANALYSIS (when available):

- Race/Ethnicity: Primary visual assessment of facial features, skin tone
- Gender: Visual presentation (appearance, clothing, mannerisms)
- Age: Visual appearance (facial features, hair, physical characteristics)
- Language: Can support audio analysis with lip movements

AUDIO ANALYSIS (always available in video or as separate audio):

- Gender: Vocal pitch and timbre (deep pitch -> Male, high pitch -> Female)
- Age: Vocal characteristics (youthful energy vs. mature tone vs. older/quavering voice)
- Language: Primary method for identifying spoken languages and accents

- Race/Ethnicity: MAY provide supporting evidence via accent, but use LOW confidence

****TRANSCRIPT/CAPTION ANALYSIS (when available):****

- Language: Confirms which languages are spoken
- Speaker identification: Helps count unique individuals
- Context: Provides semantic understanding of the interaction
- Names/References: May help distinguish between speakers

****CROSS-MODAL VERIFICATION:****

- When you have both video and audio, verify gender and age across both modalities
- Use transcript to confirm language identification from audio
- Count unique individuals by combining visual appearances with distinct voices
- Higher confidence when multiple modalities agree

DEMOGRAPHIC CATEGORIES TO IDENTIFY:

1. RACE/ETHNICITY (select all that apply):

- White: European descent appearance
- Black: African descent appearance
- Asian: East/Southeast/South Asian appearance
- Indigenous: Native American/Aboriginal appearance
- Arab: Middle Eastern/North African appearance
- Hispanic: Latin American appearance
- Note: Primarily visual assessment. Audio-only inference should have LOW confidence unless very strong accent indicators.

2. GENDER (select all that apply):

- Male: Masculine presenting individuals OR deep vocal pitch
- Female: Feminine presenting individuals OR high vocal pitch
- Use visual cues first, audio cues second

3. AGE GROUPS (select all that apply):

- Young (18-24): Visual appearance OR youthful voice
- Middle (25-39): Visual appearance OR mature voice
- Older adults (40+): Visual appearance OR older voice characteristics
- Combine visual and audio cues for best accuracy

4. LANGUAGE (select all spoken):

- Identify all languages and distinct accents heard
- Use audio AND transcript to confirm
- Default to ["English"] if only English is spoken

ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY (MULTIMODAL):

****Step 1: IDENTIFY INDIVIDUALS****

- Count unique people visible in video
- Count unique voices in audio (use transcript speaker labels if available)
- Total = unique individuals across both modalities

****Step 2: ASSESS EACH INDIVIDUAL****

For each person:

- If visible: Use video for race, gender, age (HIGH confidence)
- If speaking: Use audio for gender, age, language (MEDIUM-HIGH confidence)
- If both: Cross-verify and use HIGHEST confidence
- Use transcript to confirm language and count speakers

****Step 3: ASSIGN CONFIDENCE****

- 0.9-1.0: Clear visual evidence OR audio + visual agreement
- 0.7-0.89: Clear audio evidence OR single modality with good clarity

- 0.5-0.69: Uncertain (e.g., accent-based inference, unclear visuals)
- Below 0.5: Do not include

****Step 4: LIST UNIQUE DEMOGRAPHICS****

- Aggregate all unique demographics across all individuals
- Include only those meeting minimum confidence threshold

OUTPUT FORMAT:

Return ONLY this JSON structure with no additional text:

```
{
  "demographics_detailed": {
    "race": [list unique races observed with sufficient confidence],
    "gender": [list unique genders observed with sufficient confidence],
    "age": [list unique age groups observed with sufficient confidence],
    "language": [list languages/accent actually spoken]
  },
  "demographics_confidence": {
    "race": {"race1": confidence1, "race2": confidence2},
    "gender": {"gender1": confidence1, "gender2": confidence2},
    "age": {"age1": confidence1, "age2": confidence2},
    "language": {"language1": confidence1}
  },
  "demographics_annotation": {
    "model": "{model_name}",
    "annotated_at": "{timestamp}",
    "individuals_count": total_number_of_unique_individuals,
    "modalities_used": [list of "video", "audio", "transcript" that were available],
    "explanation": "Brief factual description combining
    visual, audio, and transcript observations."
  }
}
```

CRITICAL REMINDERS:

- Use ALL available modalities (video, audio, transcript) together
- Cross-verify demographics across modalities for higher confidence
- Return ONLY valid JSON
- No text before or after the JSON
- Empty arrays are acceptable if no confident matches found

Task 1: Summarization Generation Prompt.

Task 1: AI Annotation Generation (Map Phase)

You are a precise video segment summarizer.

SEGMENT INFORMATION:

- Segment time: {start_time}s to {end_time}s ({duration}s duration)
- Video title: {title}
- Topic: {topic_name}

TRANSCRIPT/CAPTIONS:

{transcript_text}

YOUR TASK:

Summarize this video segment concisely and accurately.

RULES:

- Maximum {max_words} words

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- Keep strict chronology - describe events in the order they occur
- Prefer facts that are audible in the transcript or visible in the video
- If nothing meaningful happens, state "No salient events in this segment"
- Be specific: include names, actions, objects, and key details
- Do NOT speculate beyond what you see/hear

OUTPUT FORMAT (JSON):

```
{
  "segment_start": "{start_time}",
  "segment_end": "{end_time}",
  "summary": "120 words maximum describing what happens in this segment...",
  "mini_timeline": [
    {"time": "MM:SS", "title": "Event name", "note": "One line description"},
    {"time": "MM:SS", "title": "Another event", "note": "Brief detail"}
  ],
  "entities": ["names", "objects", "places", "key terms mentioned"],
  "confidence": 0.85
}
```

CRITICAL:

- Return ONLY valid JSON
- No markdown, no extra text
- Timestamps in mini_timeline should be relative to SEGMENT start time
- Include 2-5 timeline items for this segment

Begin analysis:

Task 1: AI Annotation Generation (Reduce Phase)

You are an editor merging ordered segment summaries into a comprehensive video summary.

VIDEO INFORMATION:

- Video ID: {video_id}
- Title: {title}
- Topic: {topic_name}
- Total duration: {duration}s
- Number of segments: {num_segments}

SEGMENT SUMMARIES:

{segment_summaries_json}

YOUR TASK:

Merge these segment summaries into a single comprehensive video summary.

PRODUCE:

1. TL;DR: {num_bullets} concise bullet points
2. Detailed summary: {max_words_detailed} words (structure: Purpose -> Key Points -> Outcomes)
3. Global timeline: {timeline_min}-{timeline_max} items covering the entire video
4. Glossary: {glossary_min}-{glossary_max} key entities/terms from the full video

RULES:

- Remove duplicates across segments
- Keep strict chronological order
- Be concise and factual
- Prefer events that appear in multiple segments or are clearly important
- Timeline should span from video start to end with actual timestamps (HH:MM:SS format)
- Glossary should include: people's names, important objects, locations, technical terms

OUTPUT FORMAT (JSON):

```
{
  "summary_short": [
    ". First key point...",
    ". Second key point...",
    ". Third key point...",
    ". Fourth key point...",
    ". Fifth key point..."
  ],
  "summary_detailed": "200-300 word comprehensive summary.
  Start with the video's purpose,
  cover key points in chronological order, and conclude with
  outcomes or main takeaways...",
  "timeline": [
    {
      "start": "00:00:12",
      "end": "00:00:45",
      "title": "Introduction",
      "note": "Brief description"
    },
    {
      "start": "00:05:30",
      "end": "00:06:15",
      "title": "Main topic",
      "note": "Key details"
    },
    {
      "start": "00:12:00",
      "end": "00:13:30",
      "title": "Conclusion",
      "note": "Final points"
    }
  ],
  "glossary": ["Entity 1", "Entity 2", "Important Term", "Key Person", "Location"],
  "confidence": 0.88
}
```

CRITICAL:

- Return ONLY valid JSON
- No markdown, no extra text
- Timeline timestamps must be in HH:MM:SS format relative to VIDEO start
- Confidence should reflect how well segments agreed and information quality

Begin merging

Task 2: Multiple-Choice Question Generation Prompt.

Task 2: AI Annotation Generation

You are a meticulous multimodal annotator creating challenging multiple-choice questions that test deep understanding of the content.

SEGMENT INFORMATION:

- Video ID: {video_id}
- Topic: {topic_name}
- Time range: {start_time}s to {end_time}s
- Duration: {duration}s

TRANSCRIPT/CAPTIONS:

{transcript_text}

YOUR TASK:

Create challenging, thought-provoking multiple-choice questions that require reasoning and inference to answer correctly.

MULTIMODAL UNDERSTANDING FOCUS:

This task tests a model's ability to comprehend and reason about:

- Visual information: Actions, objects, settings, body language, demonstrations, equipment, text on screen
- Auditory information: Spoken dialogue, explanations, tone, background sounds, verbal instructions
- Integrated understanding: Connecting what is shown with what is said to form complete understanding

CRITICAL: Questions should naturally require multiple sources of information when possible

- Prioritize questions where explanations clarify what is demonstrated (or vice versa)
- Create questions about relationships between actions and explanations
- Test understanding that requires integrating multiple cues

QUESTION DIFFICULTY REQUIREMENTS:

AVOID simple recall questions - Don't ask questions that can be answered by simply remembering one fact.

PREFER questions that require:

- Integration: "Based on the procedure shown and the safety warnings mentioned, what complication is being prevented?"
- Correlation: "What is the key difference between the described technique and the demonstrated approach?"
- Inference: "What condition is most likely being assessed based on the complaints and examination techniques?"
- Guided Analysis: "According to the explanation, what is the purpose of the specific hand positioning observed?"
- Application: "If a patient presented with the symptoms described and signs shown, which intervention would be most appropriate?"
- Cause-and-effect: "What is the physiological reason mentioned for the clinical finding observed?"

Question complexity guidelines:

- Require connecting 2-3 pieces of information
- Ask "why" or "how" questions that need comprehensive understanding
- Test comprehension of relationships between different elements
- Require understanding of underlying principles from available evidence
- Questions should be 15-30 words to allow for complexity

OPTIONS REQUIREMENTS:

- Provide EXACTLY {num_options} options labeled (A) through ({last_option_letter})
- The LAST option ({last_option_letter}) must ALWAYS be:
"({last_option_letter}) Not enough evidence"
- IMPORTANT: "Not enough evidence" IS a valid correct answer when:
 - * The content doesn't provide sufficient information to answer confidently
 - * Multiple interpretations are equally plausible from the evidence
 - * Key information needed for reasoning is missing
 - * The question requires inference beyond what can be reasonably concluded
- Use "Not enough evidence" as the correct answer approximately 10-15% of the time
- For content-based answers (positions A through {second_to_last_letter}), create principled distractors:
 - * One near-miss (plausible but incorrect reasoning)
 - * One salient decoy (addresses part of the question but misses integration)
 - * One partial trap (correct if considering incomplete information)
 - * The correct answer (requires proper comprehensive understanding)

ANSWER POSITION DISTRIBUTION:

- Distribute correct answers evenly across ALL {num_options} positions (~{distribution_percentage}% each)
- DO NOT favor middle positions - Consciously vary answer placement
- DO NOT avoid position ({last_option_letter}) - Use it when genuinely appropriate

EVIDENCE TAGS:

Choose from this controlled vocabulary ONLY:

{evidence_tags_list}

Use tags that are actually present in the content.

requires_audio:

- Set to true when transcript/audio is NECESSARY to answer correctly
- Set to false ONLY if visual information alone is sufficient
- Default to true for questions requiring comprehensive understanding

OUTPUT FORMAT:

CRITICAL: Return a SINGLE JSON object (not an array):

```
{
  "question": "string",
  "options": ["(A) ...", "(B) ...", "(C) ...", "(D) ...",
             "({last_option_letter}) Not enough evidence"],
  "answer_index": integer (0-{{max_index}}),
  "answer_letter": "string (A-{{last_option_letter}})",
  "rationale": "string",
  "evidence_tags": ["tag1", "tag2"],
  "requires_audio": boolean,
  "confidence": float (0.0-1.0)
}
```

CRITICAL RULES:

- Return ONLY ONE JSON object (not an array)
- Return ONLY valid JSON with no markdown, no extra text
- DO NOT wrap in ``json`` markers
- DO NOT include "Question:" prefix
- Each option MUST include its letter: "(A)", "(B)", etc.
- Include BOTH "answer_index" AND "answer_letter"
- The last option must ALWAYS be "({last_option_letter}) Not enough evidence"
- USE "Not enough evidence" as correct answer ~10-15% of the time
- Distribute correct answers evenly across ALL positions
(~{{distribution_percentage}}% each)
- Only use evidence_tags from the provided list
- Questions must require reasoning, inference, or application (15-30 words)

Now generate ONE MCQ question as a single JSON object for this segment:

Task 3: Temporal Localization Generation Prompt.

Task 3: AI Annotation Generation

You are a careful video annotator creating temporal reasoning questions.

VIDEO CONTEXT:

- Video ID: {video_id}
- Duration: {duration} seconds (you are watching from 0.0s to {duration}s)
- Target: Generate {num_questions} questions
- Time unit: SECONDS (all timestamps must be decimal seconds)

TRANSCRIPT (if available):

{transcript_text}

=====

STEP 1: WATCH AND UNDERSTAND THE VIDEO

=====

First, watch the entire video carefully from start to finish.

- Note major events, actions, and scene changes
- Pay attention to both audio (speech, sounds) and visual (actions, objects) cues
- Observe the temporal flow and relationships between events

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- Prefer anchors tied to sharp audio/speech events (because they are easier to re-locate)

While watching, internally number events in the order they occur: E1, E2, E3, ... You will refer to these IDs in your rationale to make the temporal chain unambiguous.

```
=====
STEP 2: IDENTIFY KEY EVENTS WITH PRECISE TIMESTAMPS
=====
```

As you watch, note down significant events with their exact timing in DECIMAL SECONDS:

CRITICAL TIMESTAMP FORMAT:

[OK] ALWAYS use decimal seconds: 5.2, 45.0, 78.5, 125.0

[X] NEVER use MM:SS format: 1:18, 2:30, 5:45

[X] NEVER concatenate minutes+seconds: "1 minute 18 seconds" is 78.0, NOT 118

CONVERSION RULE (important!):

- If you think "1 minute 18 seconds" -> calculate $1 \times 60 + 18 = 78.0$ seconds

- If you think "2 minutes 30 seconds" -> calculate $2 \times 60 + 30 = 150.0$ seconds

- If you think "5 seconds" -> write 5.0 seconds

Example event list (create your own):

- Person says "hello" at 5.2 seconds
- Door closes at 23.8 seconds
- Phone rings at 67.5 seconds
- Person picks up phone at 71.0 seconds

All times must be between 0.0 and {duration}.

```
=====
STEP 3: PLAN YOUR QUESTIONS
=====
```

Now select {num_questions} event pairs that have clear temporal relationships.

For each question, identify:

1. ANCHOR event (the reference point) | ideally something sharp like speech or a distinct visual change
2. TARGET event (what we're searching for)
3. TEMPORAL RELATION between them

TEMPORAL RELATIONS TO USE (mix these):

after - Target occurs sometime after anchor completes

Example: "After the speaker says 'let's begin', when does the camera show the desk?"

once_finished - Target occurs immediately after anchor completes

Example: "Once the woman finishes writing, when does she turn around?"

next - Target is the next occurrence of a similar action/person/event

Example: "When is the next time the teacher speaks after the student asks a question?"

during - Target happens while anchor is ongoing

Example: "While the blue slide is displayed, when does the speaker point to the chart?"

before - Target happens before anchor (use sparingly)

Example: "Before the host introduces the guest, when does the music start?"

QUALITY CHECKS FOR EACH QUESTION:

- Both anchor and target clearly exist in the video
- There's a genuine temporal relationship (not random)
- The question tests temporal reasoning, not just recognition
- Timestamps are verifiable by watching the video
- Question is specific and unambiguous
- CRITICAL: end_s captures the COMPLETE event, not just when it begins
 - For speech: end when speaker finishes the complete thought/sentence
 - For actions: end when action fully completes
 - For visual elements: end when element disappears or transitions away

=====

STEP 4: VERIFY YOUR TIMESTAMPS

=====

For each question you plan to generate:

VERIFICATION CHECKLIST:

1. [OK] Locate anchor event -> Note time in decimal seconds
2. [OK] Locate target event START -> Note time in decimal seconds
3. [OK] Locate target event END -> Watch until event FULLY COMPLETES
 - Don't stop at first appearance - watch the entire event unfold
 - For speech: wait until the speaker finishes the complete sentence/explanation
 - For actions: wait until action concludes (not just begins)
 - For visual elements: note when they disappear or transition
4. [OK] Verify temporal relationship is correct
5. [OK] Double-check: converted MM:SS to pure seconds correctly?
6. [OK] Confirm both times are between 0.0 and {duration}
7. If two plausible target moments are <0.4 seconds apart AND the video frame rate is unknown → treat this as ambiguous and abstain

EXAMPLE VERIFICATION:

- I observe an event that appears to be "1 minute 23 seconds" into video
- CALCULATION: 1 x 60 + 23 = 83 seconds
- [OK] CORRECT: Write "start_s": 83.0
- [X] WRONG: Write "start_s": 123 (this is concatenation error!)
- [X] WRONG: Write "start_s": "1:23" (wrong format!)

=====

STEP 5: GENERATE JSON OUTPUT

=====

Now output EXACTLY {num_questions} questions in JSON array format:

```
[
  {
    "question_index": 0,
    "question": "After [anchor description], when does [target description] happen?",
    "temporal_relation": "after|once_finished|next|during|before",
    "anchor_event": "Brief description of anchor",
    "target_event": "Brief description of target",
    "answer": {
      "start_s": 78.5,
      "end_s": 82.0
    },
    "requires_audio": true,
    "confidence": 0.9,
    "abstained": false,
    "rationale_model": "E1 (anchor) at 65.0s -> E2 (target) at 78.5s,
      relation=after, target spans 78.5-82.0s.
      All times in seconds."
  },
  ...
]
```

```

]

REQUIRED FIELDS (do not add or remove fields):
- question_index: 0, 1, 2, ... (integers starting from 0)
- question: Natural language question in English
- temporal_relation: Must be one of: after, once_finished, next, during, before
- anchor_event: One sentence describing the anchor
- target_event: One sentence describing the target
- answer.start_s: Decimal seconds when target BEGINS (or null if abstained)
- answer.end_s: Decimal seconds when target COMPLETES/ENDS (or null if abstained)
  CRITICAL: end_s must capture when the event FINISHES, not just when it starts
  For speech events: end when the complete sentence/thought finishes
  For visual events: end when element disappears or transitions away
  For actions: end when the action fully completes
- requires_audio: true if audio is needed to answer, false if purely visual
- confidence: Float 0.0-1.0 indicating your certainty
- abstained: true only if target event does not exist in video OR events are
  too temporally close to disambiguate
- rationale_model: Detailed explanation with timestamps in decimal seconds
  - Keep rationale concise (<= 80 words)
  - Refer to event IDs E1, E2, ... to make the sequence clear
  - Always restate anchor time and target time (both start AND end)

ABSTENTION RULES:
- If anchor exists but target does NOT exist → Set abstained=true, answer times=null
- If temporal relationship cannot be determined → Set abstained=true, answer times=null
- If two plausible target moments are closer than 0.4 seconds → Set abstained=true,
  answer times=null
- Provide clear explanation in rationale_model

CRITICAL REQUIREMENTS:
[OK] Generate EXACTLY {num_questions} question objects
[OK] Use ONLY decimal seconds (5.2, 78.0, 125.5) - NEVER MM:SS format
[OK] Convert any MM:SS thinking to seconds: (M x 60 + S)
[OK] All times must be between 0.0 and {duration}
[OK] Return ONLY the JSON array (no markdown, no extra text)
[OK] Do NOT fabricate events that don't exist in the video
[OK] Include detailed rationale with specific timestamps
[OK] Keep rationale concise (<= 80 words) and refer to E1, E2, ...

[X] Do NOT use MM:SS format in answer fields (like 1:18 or 2:30)
[X] Do NOT concatenate minutes and seconds (78 is NOT "one eighteen")
[X] Do NOT output markdown code blocks or explanations
[X] Do NOT create questions where anchor=target
[X] Do NOT skip required fields

Now begin your annotation process following ALL five steps above.
Think carefully about timestamps - convert any MM:SS to decimal seconds!
Output your JSON array:

```

A.8. Task-Specific Annotation Procedures

Task 1: Video summarization. This task evaluates comprehension of the full recording. For videos under 10 minutes, we summarize the full audio-visual input and captions directly. Longer videos are split into 10-minute segments (with a shorter final segment); each segment is summarized independently and merged during the reducing phase into (i) a narrative summary and (ii) a bullet-point summary. Summaries emphasize causal structure, key actions, and outcomes. Any model-generated drafts are edited or rewritten by humans for correctness and style.

Task 2: Multiple-Choice Questions (MCQs). For closed-ended evaluation, videos longer than 3 minutes are segmented with 30-second overlaps to preserve context. For each segment, we generate one MCQ with four answer choices plus a fifth option (“*Not enough evidence*”) for cases where the segment does not provide sufficient information. Each MCQ is

accompanied by a brief rationale that explicitly references visual and auditory cues supporting the correct answer.

Task 3: Temporal localization. This task evaluates temporal grounding and event ordering. Using the same segmentation as the MCQ task, we construct multiple questions per segment based on an *anchor event* and a *target event* occurring before, after, during, or immediately following the anchor. During annotation, human annotators watch each segment independently and provide timestamps *relative to the segment start* (0.0s to segment duration), which then converted to absolute time by adding the segment start time to the relative predictions giving the ground truth annotations. The dataset contains 3,392 instances, with up to three questions per segment, each annotated with the correct relation, temporal interval, and a supporting rationale. This enables evaluation of both localization accuracy and temporal reasoning quality.

Ethical and licensing compliance. All datasets comply with their original licenses (e.g., Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0), research-only use) and respect data provenance and API terms. Personally identifiable or sensitive content is excluded wherever it cannot be ethically anonymized. Our process aligns with responsible AI and data governance standards (e.g., EU AI Act and NIST AI RMF principles).

B. Team and Annotation / Review Guidelines

B.1. Team Formation

The annotation team consisted of 5 domain experts with strong English proficiency and research experience in vision-language learning: 2 PhD holders, 2 Master’s students, and 1 research scientist. The team composition was gender-balanced (2 male, 3 female) and geographically diverse, with members from East Asia, Middle East, North America, and South Asia. All annotators completed task-specific training before beginning annotation work. The annotation workflow followed a hierarchical review structure: Master’s students conducted initial annotations, which were reviewed by PhD holders, with the research scientist providing final oversight and quality control. The team held weekly calibration meetings to discuss edge cases, resolve annotation disagreements, and ensure consistency across the dataset.

When disagreements arose, they were escalated to the weekly calibration meetings and resolved synchronously through discussion among domain experts. Annotators compared their rationales against the labeling guidelines and the available evidence from the multimodal inputs (video, audio, and captions). We explicitly solicited perspectives from multiple domain experts to reduce individual bias and clarify ambiguous cases. Decisions were made by consensus when possible; otherwise we adopted a majority vote among the reviewing domain experts, with the research scientist serving as the final tie-breaker and recording the final decision to maintain consistency.

B.2. Guidelines

To ensure annotation quality and consistency, annotators followed these core principles:

Annotation Quality Checklist

Before Starting Annotation:

- Specify the topic being annotated (e.g., Topic 2: Job Interviews)
- Specify the task being reviewed (Task 1: Summarization / Task 2: MCQ / Task 3: Temporal Localization)
- Watch the entire video fully before annotation
- Review any available captions or transcripts for context

During Annotation:

- Ground all questions, answers, and rationales in observable audio-visual content
- Flag cases with insufficient evidence rather than making assumptions
- Assign demographic attributes based on visual and auditory presentation in the video
- Revisit any timestamp as needed to verify accuracy
- Discuss ambiguous cases with team leads before finalizing

Quality Control:

- Ensure all required fields are completed (question, answer, rationale, timestamps where applicable)
- Verify that rationales explicitly reference audio-visual evidence
- Check for internal consistency within annotations you reviewed

After Review:

- Address reviewer feedback and revise annotations as needed
- Participate in weekly calibration meetings to discuss edge cases
- Update annotations based on refined guidelines from team discussions

For task-specific protocols (segmentation, timestamps, rationale structure), see Section A.8.

B.3. Review Interface

We developed a custom web-based review interface to facilitate efficient human verification and correction of AI-generated annotations. The interface supports all three annotation tasks and provides real-time video playback, synchronized captions, and structured editing fields.

Quality filtering interface. Figure A2 shows the initial quality filtering interface used during video selection. Reviewers assess each candidate video for topic relevance, audio-visual quality, and demographic coverage, marking videos as either “Good” or “Bad” for inclusion in the dataset.

Task-specific review interfaces. Figures A3, A4, and A5 illustrate the task-specific interfaces for editing and validating annotations across the three tasks. Each interface provides:

- **Video player:** Embedded YouTube player with timestamp controls and caption display
- **Edit fields:** Structured input fields for questions, answers, rationales, and timestamps
- **Demographics panel:** JSON editor for verifying and correcting demographic labels with per-person annotations
- **Navigation controls:** Previous/Next buttons, jump functionality, and session management
- **Auto-save:** Changes persist automatically when navigating between items

The interface ensures high annotation quality by requiring annotators to watch full videos, providing easy access to AI-generated drafts for comparison, and supporting rapid iteration across large annotation batches.

Figure A2. Quality filtering interface for initial video selection. Reviewers watch candidate videos and label them as “Good” or “Bad” based on inclusion criteria (audio-visual quality, topic relevance, demographic coverage). The interface displays video metadata (duration, topic category, licensing) and allows batch processing with session management.

VQA Review & Edit Tool
 Edit and validate AI-generated video understanding annotations

Instructions

1. Select a **task type** and **topic**
2. Watch the video and read the caption
3. **Edit the fields below** to correct any errors
4. Changes **auto-save** when you navigate

1. Select Task Type: task_summarization | 2. Select Topic: 01_Patient-Doctor_Consultations | Load

Loaded 16 items from vqa/task1_summarization/01_Patient-Doctor_Consultations.json for session be81edbf.

Item 1 / 16 | Video: 001

Video

How to Take a Patient History (full guide) | KharmaMedic

TAKE A PATIENT HISTORY

Watch on YouTube

Caption

reorganizing them into my history taking.

218
 00:15:05,774 --> 00:15:06,677
 Thanks so much for watching.

219
 00:15:06,797 --> 00:15:09,546
 I hope you find this video useful and I will catch you in the next one.

220
 00:15:10,148 --> 00:15:10,609
 Peace.

Edit Data

Summary (Short) - one bullet point per line

- Nasser (Kharmamedic) introduces a comprehensive guide to taking patient histories, starting with crucial pre-history steps like understanding context and building rapport.
- He outlines the general history structure, emphasizing the 'ICE' framework, then details approaching patients with WJPER and exploring presenting complaints using SOCRATES and DOPT.
- The guide then covers a comprehensive systems review, including constitutional symptoms, and delves into past medical history, highlighting chronic conditions and the JAMTHREADS mnemonic.
- It further explains drug history, emphasizing current medications, side effects, and allergies, followed by family history focused on hereditary conditions.
- Finally, the video details social history (lifestyle, occupation, HEADSSS, ADLs) and provides a bonus tip to re-address patient's ICE (Ideas, Concerns, Expectations) if unsure.

Summary (Detailed)

This initial segment features Nasser, a final-year medical student from King's College London (Kharmamedic), as he introduces a detailed guide on how to take patient histories effectively. He begins by providing a disclaimer, clarifying the content's educational nature. Nasser then outlines essential steps to take before engaging with a patient, such as understanding the clinical context and establishing rapport. He explains the general structure of a patient history, highlighting the 'ICE' framework (Ideas, Concerns, Expectations) to gain insight into the patient's viewpoint. The segment further elaborates on how to properly approach a patient using the WJPER acronym (Washing hands, Introducing self, Patient details, Exploring, Re-position) and securing verbal consent. Finally, Nasser provides guidance on exploring the 'presenting complaint' and 'history of presenting complaint' by utilizing open-ended questions and mnemonic acronyms like SOCRATES for pain and DOPT for duration, onset, progression, and timing, stressing the importance of summarizing information back to the patient. Building on this, the video then details the latter parts of taking a patient's history, starting with a comprehensive systems review, including constitutional symptoms like fevers and unexplained weight loss. Next, the video explains the past medical history, stressing the importance of chronic conditions, past surgeries, hospital admissions, and mentions the JAMTHREADS mnemonic. The drug history follows, covering current medications, recent changes, potential side effects, and crucially, allergies. The family history section advises asking about hereditary illnesses and sensitivity when discussing deceased relatives. The social history includes questions about smoking, drinking, recreational drugs, occupation, living situation, and mnemonics like HEADSSS for adolescents and ADLs for the elderly. Finally, a bonus tip is provided: if unsure, ask the patient what they think caused their symptoms or what concerns them, reinforcing the ICE framework.

Demographics (JSON)

Edit demographics as JSON array

```

1 [
2 {
3   "name": "Nasser",
4   "gender": "Male",
5   "age": "Young (18-24)",
6   "language": "English",
7   "count": 1
8 }
9 ]
    
```

Previous | Save | Next | Go to Question # | Jump

File Information

Figure A3. Review interface for Task 1 (Video Summarization). Annotators edit AI-generated summaries (both detailed and bullet-point formats) while watching the full video with synchronized captions. The demographics panel allows verification and correction of demographic labels in JSON format. Changes auto-save when navigating between items.

VQA Review & Edit Tool
 Edit and validate AI-generated video understanding annotations

Instructions

1. Select a **task type** and **topic**
2. Watch the video and read the caption
3. **Edit the fields below** to correct any errors
4. Changes **auto-save** when you navigate

1. Select Task Type: task2_mcq | 2. Select Topic: 05_Courtroom_Proceedings | Load

Loaded 117 items from vqa/task2_mcq/05_Courtroom_Proceedings.json for session be81edbf.

Item 1 / 117 | Video: 001

Video

Footloose Sentenced for "Disorderly Conduct", Goes Off on Court Goons!

Segment: 00:00 - 03:30

Caption

95
00:03:56,622 --> 00:04:00,046
Library doesn't have strikes or any way to take down videos.

96
00:04:00,026 --> 00:04:01,891
Our days are numbered on YouTube.

97
00:04:01,912 --> 00:04:10,155
Get the app at lbrly.com or follow our channel on library's new platform, Odyssey, at video.freekeen.com.

Edit Data

Question
Footloose attributes his previous conviction for disorderly conduct, which he considers 'persecution' to what personal characteristic mentioned during his current hearing?

Options (one per line)

(A) His political activism, as evidenced by his shirt and speech.
 (B) His tendency to become loud and hyper-aggressive due to a disability.
 (C) His deliberate choice to speak loudly in defense of his First Amendment rights.
 (D) The misinterpretation of his non-disruptive behavior by law enforcement.
 (E) Not enough evidence

Correct Answer Letter
B

Rationale (Explanation)
At 01:37-01:41, Footloose explicitly states, "So I got found guilty of disorderly conduct for having a disability because I get excited and hyper-aggressive." This directly links his conviction to his personal characteristic of having a disability that leads to loud and hyper-aggressive behavior. While he mentions First Amendment rights and his shirt suggests activism, his direct explanation for the conviction's basis is related to a disability.

Requires Audio (true/false)
True

Demographics Explanation
The segment shows one female attorney (Middle age), one male defendant (Middle age), three male police officers (appearing Middle age), one male judge (Older adult), two male audience members (Older adults), one female audience member (Older adult), and one male cameraman (Older adult). All speak English.

Demographics (JSON)

```

Edit demographics as JSON array
1 {
2 {
3   "race": "White",
4   "gender": "Female",
5   "age": "Middle (25-39)",
6   "language": "English",
7   "count": 1
8 }
9 {
10  "race": "White",
11  "gender": "Male",
12  "age": "Middle (25-39)",
13  "language": "English",
14  "count": 4
15 }
16 {
17  "race": "White",
18  "gender": "Female",
19  "count": 1
20 }

```

Figure A4. Review interface for Task 2 (Multiple-Choice Questions). Annotators review and edit MCQ questions, answer options (A–E), correct answer labels, and rationales that reference visual and auditory evidence. The segment indicator shows the current 3-minute video segment being annotated.

VQA Review & Edit Tool
 Edit and validate AI-generated video understanding annotations

Instructions

1. Select a **task type** and **topic**
2. Watch the video and read the caption
3. **Edit the fields below** to correct any errors
4. Changes **auto-save** when you navigate

1. Select Task Type: task3_temporal_localization | 2. Select Topic: 13_Olympics | Load

Loaded 105 items from 'vqa/task3_temporal_localization/13_Olympics.json' for session be81edbf.
 Item 7 / 105 | Video: 004

Video

WALLAROOS vs FIJIANA MATCH HIGHLIGHTS 2022

Segment: 00:44 - 03:30

Jump to Segment

Caption

Thus far with ball in hand, Tatakai to Patu again.

18
 00:01:02,850 --> 00:01:04,733
 And here goes Liz Patu.

19
 00:01:05,724 --> 00:01:06,825
 Still going.

20
 00:01:06,906 --> 00:01:08,308
 To the right, if they can get it there.

21

Edit Data

Question
 After the referee signals a penalty try for Australia, when does Fiji score their first try?

Temporal Relation
 after

Anchor Event
 The referee signals a penalty try for Australia by raising her arm and confirming with the TMO

Target Event
 Fiji score their first try by pushing the ball over the line

Answer Start (seconds): 44.0 | **Answer End (seconds)**: 49.715

Rationale (Explanation)
 E1 (referee signals penalty try for AUS) occurs at 32.514s and completes at 33.917s. E2 (Fiji score their first try) starts at 44.0s and completes at 49.715s. Relation = after.

Requires Audio (true/false)
 True

Demographics Explanation
 The video primarily features female rugby players and a female referee, all speaking English. Players are distributed across 'Young' and 'Middle' age categories. Based on visual assessment and team compositions (Wallaroos and Fiji), individuals were categorized into White, Indigenous, and Black races as per the provided ground truth, making a reasonable distribution for each unique combination.

Demographics (JSON)

Edit demographics as JSON array

```

1 [
2   {
3     "race": "White",
4     "gender": "Female",
5     "age": "Young (18-24)",
6     "language": "English",
7     "count": 5
8   },

```

Figure A5. Review interface for Task 3 (Temporal Localization). Annotators edit anchor-target event pairs, temporal relations (before/after/during/immediately), answer start/end timestamps, rationales explaining the temporal reasoning, and audio requirements. The segment timeline helps annotators identify precise event boundaries within 3-minute video segments.

Figure A6. Video duration analysis by topic. (a) Distribution showing the count of short (orange), medium (teal), and long (dark teal) videos within each of the 13 topics. Housing/Apartment Tours contains the most videos (24), while Workplace Team Meetings has the fewest (12). (b) Average duration per topic, with Parent-Teacher Conferences having the longest average (36.2 min) and Customer Service Interactions the shortest (6.0 min).

C. Extended Dataset Statistics

C.1. Demographic Distribution

Figure A7 reports the demographic distribution *at the benchmark instance level*. Counts reflect how often demographic groups appear across all benchmark instances (Task 1 chunks and Task 2–3 segments), using per-instance demographic counts/mappings, rather than the number of **unique individuals** or **unique videos**. As a result, the same individuals may be counted multiple times across different segments or tasks when the underlying content is reused.

This aggregated view should be interpreted as **demographic exposure frequency** in the benchmark. It is appropriate for evaluating model behavior, since models are evaluated on these instances, but it does not represent a census of unique participants.

We observe moderate skew toward male-presenting speakers and participants aged 40+, which likely reflects the underlying distribution of English-language CC BY 4.0 YouTube content in our target domains. Topics with large groups (e.g., community town halls and courtroom proceedings) further increase exposure counts because many individuals co-occur and persist across multiple segments.

C.2. Video Duration Statistics

Figures A6a, and A6b illustrate the distribution of video durations across the three length categories (Short: <5 minutes, Medium: 5-20 minutes, Long: 20-60 minutes) and by topic.

D. Preprocessing and Inference Configuration

D.1. Hardware-Aware Inference Constraints

To rigorously assess open-source MLLMs, we utilize a standardized compute environment of **4× NVIDIA A40 GPUs (40GB VRAM each)**. This configuration allows for substantial parallelization but imposes hard memory limits on long-context processing. A notable exception is **MiniCPM-o-2.6**, which we evaluate on a single **NVIDIA A100 (80GB)** GPU, as the official implementation does not currently support distributed inference. These hardware constraints necessitate a strict input capping and fallback policy to prevent Out-Of-Memory (OOM) failures while maximizing the multimodal context available to each model.

Figure A7. Demographic distribution of benchmark instance level (a) race/ethnicity, (b) age group, and (c) gender. Race distribution shows: White (10,997), Black (3,494), Asian (1,831), Hispanic (1,443), Indigenous (511), Arab (438). Age distribution shows: 18-24 (2,124), 25-39 (5,317), 40+ (11,173). Gender distribution shows: Male (12,672), Female (5,942).

D.2. Visual and Audio Input Strategy

We adopt a unified prompting strategy, concatenating the textual prompt, audio input, and sampled video frames, strictly adhering to each model’s official implementation.

- **Modality Fusion:** Most models ingest separated modalities (frames + audio). However, **VideoLLaMA 2** is an exception, requiring the raw video file with embedded audio rather than discrete inputs.
- **Visual Capping:** We cap the initial maximum visual input at $F_{\max} = 256$ frames. This limit was empirically determined to fit within the memory constraints of our $4 \times A40$ setup for the majority of architectures.

D.3. Robustness and Adaptive Fallback Protocols

To ensure evaluation fairness across diverse architectures, we enforce a consistent, dynamic fallback protocol for models that encounter Out-Of-Memory (OOM) errors or context overflow. We initiate inference with each model’s designated maximum frame capacity: 256 frames for Qwen3-Omni, UniMoE-2.0, and MiniCPM-o-2.6; 128 frames for VideoLLaMA2; and 64 frames for VITA 1.5. These represent upper bounds; shorter videos naturally use fewer frames. All models initially receive full unchunked audio. Lower frame caps for VITA and VideoLLaMA2 reflect their smaller context windows and more limited memory footprints under our hardware constraints. Upon failure, we apply a synchronized reduction strategy:

1. **Visual Reduction:** The frame budget is iteratively halved from each model’s maximum. For example, Qwen3-Omni reduces through the sequence $\{256, 128, 64, 32\}$, allowing up to four retry attempts.
2. **Audio Reduction:** Simultaneously, we adjust audio fidelity through uniform chunk sampling rather than truncation. If the full audio track causes failure, we transition to a chunked representation with a maximum limit of $N = 64$ chunks. Each chunk spans 10 seconds of non-overlapping audio. In subsequent retries, this chunk limit halves in lockstep with visual frames through the sequence $\{64, 32, 16\}$. Given audio of duration D seconds, the natural chunk count is $M = \lceil D/10 \rceil$. When $M \leq N$, all chunks are retained; when $M > N$, we uniformly sample N chunks using indices $= \lfloor \text{linspace}(0, M - 1, N) \rfloor$ to preserve temporal coverage across the full recording.

We adopted this audio chunking because not all MLLMs handle long audio tracks, as such they employ naive audio handling strategies such as end-truncation or middle-cropping, introducing uncontrolled confounds in evaluation. Our uniform chunk sampling approach is inspired by MiniCPM-o-2.6 (Yao et al., 2024).

This “start-high, fall-back” approach ensures that reported performance reflects each model’s maximum capability under standard hardware constraints ($4 \times$ NVIDIA A40 GPUs, 40GB VRAM each or $1 \times$ NVIDIA A100, 80GB VRAM).

D.4. Task-Specific Prompts

We report the shared task instruction text (T1–T3) used across models. For open-source MLLMs, we rely on each model’s default chat template and required modality tokens/placeholders (e.g., Uni-MoE-2.0’s `<video>/<audio>` markers; VITA

1.5's image/audio special tokens) as implemented in their official codebases.

Task 1: Video Summarization.

Task 1: Standard Prompt

You are analyzing a video that is {video_duration} seconds long.

Please provide a comprehensive analysis with the following components:

1. **DETAILED SUMMARY:** Write a detailed paragraph (150-250 words) that captures the main content, key points, and flow of the video.
2. **SHORT SUMMARY:** Provide 3-5 concise bullet points highlighting the most important takeaways.
3. **TIMELINE:** Create a timeline of major sections/topics in the video with:
 - start: timestamp in "HH:MM:SS" format
 - end: timestamp in "HH:MM:SS" format
 - title: brief section title
 - note: one sentence description
4. **GLOSSARY:** List 5-15 key terms, acronyms, or important concepts mentioned in the video.
5. **CONFIDENCE:** Rate your confidence in this analysis from 0.0 to 1.0.

Return your response as a JSON object with this exact structure:

```
{
  "summary_detailed": "detailed paragraph here",
  "summary_short": ["bullet 1", "bullet 2", "bullet 3"],
  "timeline": [
    {
      "start": "00:00:00",
      "end": "00:02:30",
      "title": "Section Title",
      "note": "Brief description"
    }
  ],
  "glossary": ["term1", "term2", "term3"],
  "confidence": 0.95
}
```

Only return the JSON object, no additional text.

Task 1: Empathy Prompt

You are analyzing a video that is {video_duration} seconds long.

Please provide an empathetic and emotionally aware analysis. Focus on understanding the emotional context, interpersonal dynamics, and human elements in the content.

Provide:

1. DETAILED SUMMARY: Write a detailed, empathetic paragraph (150–250 words) that captures not just what happens, but the emotional tone, interpersonal dynamics, and human aspects. Consider how participants might feel and what underlying concerns or needs are being expressed.
2. CONFIDENCE: Rate your confidence in this analysis from 0.0 to 1.0.

Return your response as a JSON object:

```
{
  "summary_detailed_empathic": "empathetic detailed paragraph here",
  "confidence": 0.95
}
```

Only return the JSON object, no additional text.

Task 2: Multiple-Choice Question Answering.

Task 2 Prompt

You are analyzing a video segment to answer a multiple choice question.

QUESTION:
{question}

OPTIONS:
{options_text}

Please analyze the video content carefully and:

1. Select the best answer from the options
2. Provide a clear rationale explaining why this answer is correct based on what you observed in the video
3. Rate your confidence in this answer from 0.0 to 1.0

Return your response as a JSON object with this exact structure:

```
{
  "answer_letter": "B",
  "answer_index": 1,
  "rationale": "Explanation of why this answer is correct based on video
               content",
  "confidence": 0.90
}
```

Notes:

- answer_letter should be "A", "B", "C", "D", or "E"
- answer_index should be 0, 1, 2, 3, or 4 (corresponding to A, B, C, D, E)
- rationale should reference specific details from the video
- CRITICAL: include all fields in the JSON and ensure proper formatting especially answer_letter

Only return the JSON object, no additional text.

Task 3: Temporal Localization.

For temporal localization inference, models receive absolute segment boundaries and must predict timestamps in absolute video time. For example, when evaluating a 3-minute segment spanning 500–680 seconds of a 30-minute video, the model is told “You are analyzing a video segment from 500s to 680s” and must return predictions within [500s, 680s], not [0s, 180s].

This design ensures models maintain temporal awareness of their position within the full video, which is critical for long-form understanding. In contrast, during annotation (Section A.8), human annotators worked with segment-relative timestamps (0.0s to segment duration) for cognitive ease when watching isolated clips. These segment-relative annotations were automatically converted to absolute video time by adding the segment start offset, producing ground truth in the same coordinate system used during inference. This alignment between annotation conversion and inference format ensures fair evaluation: models are tested on their ability to reason about events in absolute video time, matching real-world deployment scenarios where systems must index events within full-length recordings.

The inference prompt below specifies the absolute segment range and constraints:

Task 3 Prompt

You are analyzing a video segment from {segment_start}s to {segment_end}s (duration: {segment_duration}s).

QUESTIONS ({num_questions} total):
{questions_text}

REQUIRED OUTPUT FORMAT:

```
{
  "questions": [
    {
      "question_id": "001",
      "start_s": <timestamp_float>,
      "end_s": <timestamp_float>,
      "confidence": <float_between_0_and_1>,
      "rationale_model": "<your explanation>"
    },
    {
      "question_id": "002",
      "start_s": <timestamp_float>,
      "end_s": <timestamp_float>,
      "confidence": <float_between_0_and_1>,
      "rationale_model": "<your explanation>"
    }
    ... (continue for all {num_questions} questions)
  ]
}
```

RATIONALE REQUIREMENTS:

Explain: When E1 (anchor) occurs -> When E2 (target) starts/ends ->
Temporal relationship -> Visual/audio cues

Example: "E1 (anchor) starts at 5.2s with speaker's introduction. E2 (target) starts at 35.0s when he says 'I am a final year medical student', ends at 36.6s. Relationship: 'after'."

CONSTRAINTS:

- All timestamps within [{segment_start}s, {segment_end}s]
- start_s < end_s for each question
- Include ALL {num_questions} questions with their question_id field
- CRITICAL: include all fields in the JSON and ensure proper formatting
- CRITICAL: Your response MUST include these exact question_ids: {question_ids_list} and include the question_id field
- Return ONLY valid JSON (no markdown, no code blocks, no extra text)

Table A3. Effective inference settings and preprocessing strategies. **Checkpoint** refers to the specific HuggingFace model ID used. **Native** indicates the model’s default preprocessing; **Adaptive** denotes non-native audio chunking applied as a fallback mechanism.

Model / Checkpoint	Backbone	Frames	Audio	Hardware	Notes
VideoLLaMA2.1-7B-AV	Qwen2-7B	128	Embedded	4×A40	Integrated video+audio input.
Qwen3-Omni-30B-A3B-Instruct	Qwen3-MoE	256	Adaptive*	4×A40	Chunking triggered by length overflow.
Uni-MoE-2.0-Omni	Qwen2.5-7B	256	Full	4×A40	Native processing.
MiniCPM-o-2.6	Qwen2.5-7B	256	Full	1×A100	Native processing.
VITA-1.5	Qwen2-7B	64	Adaptive*	4×A40	Chunking triggered by length overflow.
Gemini 3.0 Pro	Proprietary	1 FPS	Full	API	Native processing.
GPT-4o	Proprietary	256	Captions [†]	API	No native audio support; ASR captions used.

*Audio Chunking triggered [†]Fallback to text modality. All models use temp=0.7, top-p=0.95, max tokens=8192.

D.5. Per-Model Effective Settings

Table A3 details the effective frame budget, audio handling, and specific hardware allocation for each evaluated model.

E. Evaluation Metrics

This section provides formal definitions of all evaluation metrics used in our benchmark. Metrics are computed internally in the range $[0, 1]$ but are reported as percentages (scaled by 100) where indicated. Text similarity metrics remain in the $[0, 1]$ range following standard conventions.

E.1. Task 1: Video Summarization Metrics

For Task 1 (Video Summarization), we evaluate both detailed summaries and short bullet-point summaries using the following metrics:

ROUGE-L. We compute ROUGE-L (Longest Common Subsequence) F1-score (Lin, 2004) to measure n-gram overlap between generated and reference summaries. For a reference summary R and predicted summary P :

$$\text{ROUGE-L}(R, P) = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Prec}_{\text{LCS}} \cdot \text{Rec}_{\text{LCS}}}{\text{Prec}_{\text{LCS}} + \text{Rec}_{\text{LCS}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where Prec_{LCS} and Rec_{LCS} are precision and recall based on the longest common subsequence. The score is reported as a percentage in $[0, 100]$.

Text Similarity. We measure semantic similarity using cosine similarity between sentence embeddings. Given embeddings e_R and e_P from a pre-trained model (all-MiniLM-L6-v2):

$$\text{TextSim}(R, P) = \frac{e_R \cdot e_P}{\|e_R\| \|e_P\|} \quad (2)$$

This metric is reported in $[0, 1]$, following standard cosine similarity conventions.

Aggregation. For a dataset with N videos, we report the mean metric across all samples:

$$\overline{\text{ROUGE-L}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{ROUGE-L}(R_i, P_i) \quad (3)$$

We compute these metrics separately for detailed summaries and short summaries.

E.2. Task 2: Multiple-Choice Question Answering Metrics

For Task 2 (MCQ Question Answering), we evaluate both answer accuracy and rationale quality.

Answer Accuracy. For each question q_i with ground truth answer a_i^{gt} and predicted answer a_i^{pred} :

$$\text{Correct}(q_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a_i^{\text{pred}} = a_i^{\text{gt}} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The overall accuracy across N questions is:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{Correct}(q_i) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

reported as a percentage in $[0, 100]$.

Rationale Metrics. For each question, we evaluate the quality of the model’s rationale (explanation) using:

- **ROUGE-L:** Measures lexical overlap with reference rationale (reported as percentage, $[0, 100]$)
- **Text Similarity:** Semantic similarity via cosine distance (reported in $[0, 1]$)

We aggregate rationale metrics by computing the mean across all questions with valid rationales.

E.3. Task 3: Temporal Localization Metrics

For Task 3 (Temporal Localization), we evaluate the model’s ability to identify temporal intervals that answer questions about video segments.

Temporal Intersection over Union (tIoU). For a ground truth temporal interval $G = [s^{\text{gt}}, e^{\text{gt}}]$ and predicted interval $P = [s^{\text{pred}}, e^{\text{pred}}]$, where s and e denote start and end times in seconds:

$$\text{tIoU}(G, P) = \frac{\max(0, \min(e^{\text{gt}}, e^{\text{pred}}) - \max(s^{\text{gt}}, s^{\text{pred}}))}{\max(e^{\text{gt}}, e^{\text{pred}}) - \min(s^{\text{gt}}, s^{\text{pred}})} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

The tIoU measures temporal overlap and is reported as a percentage in $[0, 100]$.

Mean Intersection over Union (mIoU). The mean IoU aggregates tIoU scores across all N temporal localization questions:

$$\text{mIoU} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{tIoU}(G_i, P_i) \quad (7)$$

This metric is reported as a percentage in $[0, 100]$.

Recall at IoU Threshold (Recall@ θ). We measure the percentage of predictions whose tIoU meets or exceeds a threshold θ :

$$\text{Recall@}\theta = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{1}[\text{tIoU}(G_i, P_i) \geq \theta] \cdot 100 \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbb{1}[\cdot]$ is the indicator function. We report Recall@0.3, Recall@0.5, and Recall@0.7 as percentages in $[0, 100]$. We abbreviate Recall@ θ as R@ θ in tables.

Mean Absolute Error (MAE). We compute the temporal localization error for start and end times:

$$\text{MAE}_{\text{start}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |s_i^{\text{gt}} - s_i^{\text{pred}}| \quad (9)$$

$$\text{MAE}_{\text{end}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |e_i^{\text{gt}} - e_i^{\text{pred}}| \quad (10)$$

$$\text{MAE}_{\text{avg}} = \frac{\text{MAE}_{\text{start}} + \text{MAE}_{\text{end}}}{2} \quad (11)$$

MAE is reported in seconds.

Rationale Metrics. Similar to Task 2, we evaluate rationale quality using ROUGE-L (percentage) and Text Similarity ([0, 1]).

E.4. LLM-as-Judge Evaluation

For tasks involving free-form text generation (summaries, rationales), we employ an LLM-as-Judge evaluation protocol adopted from previous work to assess semantic correctness and quality beyond n-gram overlap metrics (Ataallah et al., 2025). We use GPT-5-mini (OpenAI, 2026) as our primary judge.

Evaluation Protocol. For each generated output, the judge model:

1. Receives the original question and both the reference and predicted answers
2. Evaluates semantic similarity, factual correctness, and completeness
3. Assigns a numerical score from 0 (completely incorrect) to 10 (perfect match)
4. Provides a concise justification (1-3 sentences) for the assigned score

The judge is instructed to accept paraphrases, synonyms, or rephrasings as valid when they preserve the original meaning, and to penalize omissions of key factual elements, hallucinated content, or contradictions. The evaluation focuses on semantic alignment rather than surface-level textual similarity.

Scoring Scale and Output Format. Judges assign integer scores from 0 to 10 and return responses in JSON format:

```
{
  "score": <integer 0-10>,
  "justification": "<brief explanation>"
}
```

We aggregate judge scores by computing the mean across all evaluated samples. This provides a complementary assessment to automatic metrics (ROUGE-L, cosine similarity), particularly for capturing semantic equivalence that lexical overlap metrics may miss.

Judge Prompt. The complete system prompt provided to the judge model is shown in Figure A8. The prompt emphasizes fair evaluation, human-like judgment, and consistent scoring criteria across all evaluated outputs.

E.5. Aggregation Across Topics

Our benchmark spans multiple topics (content domains). For each task, we first compute metrics within each topic, then aggregate across topics by computing the mean metric value. This approach provides a single aggregate score while accounting for performance variation across different content types. Due to space constraints in tables, we report only mean values; per-topic breakdowns are available in our supplementary materials.

System Prompt:

You are an intelligent and fair evaluator AI that specializes in assessing the correctness and semantic alignment between ground truth answers and predicted responses for question-answering tasks, including those based on video content.

Evaluation Instructions:

- Focus on **semantic similarity**, **factual correctness**, and **completeness**
- Accept paraphrases, synonyms, or rephrasings as **valid**, as long as they preserve the original meaning
- **Do not penalize** for stylistic differences or changes in tone, unless they impact factual accuracy
- **Penalize if:**
 - The predicted answer omits **key factual elements** present in the correct answer
 - The prediction includes **hallucinated content** or unfounded details
 - The prediction **contradicts** the correct answer
- Use human-like judgment: apply reasoning beyond surface text similarity
- When uncertain, provide a **conservative but fair** score
- Use a scoring scale from **0 (completely incorrect)** to **10 (perfect match)**

Output Format: Return a JSON object with two fields:

```
{
  "score": <integer from 0 to 10>,
  "justification": "<concise explanation (1-3 sentences)>"
}
```

User Prompt Template:

Please evaluate the following video-based question-answer pair:

Question: {question}

Correct Answer: {correct_answer}

Predicted Answer: {predicted_answer}

Please return your evaluation in the specified JSON format with both a score and a justification.

Figure A8. **LLM-as-Judge evaluation prompt.** The system prompt instructs the judge to evaluate semantic correctness, factual completeness, and relevance on a 0-10 scale, with specific guidelines for handling paraphrases, hallucinations, and contradictions.

E.6. Implementation Details

Libraries. We use the following libraries for metric computation:

- **ROUGE:** `rouge-score` package with Porter stemming
- **Text Embeddings:** `sentence-transformers` with `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` model
- **LLM Judge:** OpenAI API (GPT-5-mini)

Handling Failed Predictions. If a model fails to generate a prediction for a sample (e.g., due to timeout or error), that sample is excluded from metric computation. We report the number of successfully evaluated samples for each task.

Reproducibility. All metric computation code and detailed per-topic results are available in our code repository. For statistical comparison between models, we recommend paired bootstrap tests with $n = 10,000$ resamples and $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level.

F. Detailed Results

Table A4 presents the complete benchmark results across all three tasks, including all automatic metrics and LLM-as-judge rationale scores. We report detailed summarization performance, MCQ accuracy with rationale quality, and temporal localization metrics including mIoU, recall at multiple thresholds, mean absolute error, and rationale quality.

Table A4. **Comprehensive benchmark results across all tasks and metrics.** Results are reported for MLLMs on all dataset. Summarization reports judge scores (0–10), ROUGE-L (%), and similarity (0–1). MCQ reports accuracy (%) and rationale quality (score 0–10, ROUGE-L %, similarity 0–1). Temporal localization reports mIoU (%), R@0.3/R@0.5 (%), MAE in seconds, and rationale quality. **Bold** indicates best performance, underline indicates second-best.

Model	Summarization			MCQ				Temporal Localization						
	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	mIoU	R@0.3	R@0.5	MAE	Score	RG-L	Sim
Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	7.07	27.2	0.813	96.4	9.38	36.9	0.802	26.6	39.3	25.4	12.0	5.38	28.3	<u>0.673</u>
Qwen3-Omni	<u>5.72</u>	22.8	<u>0.713</u>	93.6	8.88	33.8	0.777	<u>3.70</u>	5.14	<u>2.81</u>	60.0	2.58	<u>28.0</u>	0.698
UniMoE-2.0	4.71	20.8	0.700	88.2	8.12	26.5	0.727	<u>1.81</u>	2.40	1.04	685.8	2.11	<u>23.7</u>	0.549
MiniCPM-o-2.6	3.34	14.7	0.563	87.4	8.01	24.4	0.729	1.81	2.38	0.73	367.1	3.65	19.3	0.406
VITA 1.5	<u>2.77</u>	16.3	0.491	81.6	7.72	25.2	0.714	1.81	2.55	1.15	116.1	<u>3.91</u>	22.1	0.433
VideoLLaMA2	1.53	12.7	0.383	54.4	5.11	18.9	0.577	3.50	1.68	0.42	234.5	2.22	22.5	0.493

Key findings. Gemini 3.0 Pro demonstrates strong performance across all tasks, achieving the best scores in summarization (7.07), MCQ accuracy (96.4%), and temporal localization (26.6% mIoU, 25.4% R@0.5). Qwen3-Omni achieves second-best performance on most metrics, with particularly strong rationale quality (28.0% ROUGE-L, 0.698 similarity on temporal task). Among open-source models, UniMoE-2.0 shows the best summarization capabilities, while VITA 1.5 produces the highest-quality temporal rationales (3.91 judge score).

The temporal localization task reveals a critical challenge for open-source models: all models except Gemini exhibit large MAE values (60.0–685.8 seconds), indicating systematic temporal reference frame hallucination as discussed in Appendix G. This failure mode occurs when models process long videos in segments but fail to ground predictions in absolute timestamps, instead treating each segment as starting at time 0.0 seconds. Despite this localization failure, models can still produce reasonable rationales (scores 2.11–3.91), demonstrating a disconnect between semantic understanding and temporal grounding.

Rationale quality metrics show interesting patterns: while Gemini produces the best overall rationales for summarization and MCQ tasks, Qwen3-Omni achieves competitive or superior similarity scores on temporal localization (0.698), and VITA 1.5 receives the highest judge scores for temporal rationales (3.91). This suggests that rationale quality does not perfectly correlate with task performance, and that different models may excel at explanation versus execution.

G. Detailed Results Per-Topic

This appendix provides comprehensive per-topic performance breakdowns for all three tasks. Each table reports metrics for individual topics (T1–T13), allowing detailed analysis of model capabilities across different conversational domains. All metrics follow the same conventions as the main paper: percentages for ROUGE-L, Accuracy, mIoU, and Recall; 0–1 scale for cosine similarity; 0–10 scale for LLM judge scores; seconds for MAE. Bold denotes best performance, underline denotes second-best within each topic. [†] denotes closed-source model.

G.1. Key Observations from Per-Topic Analysis

Topic-specific performance variation. Models exhibit substantial performance variation across topics. In summarization (Tables A5–A7), Gemini achieves 8.33 on T2: Job Interviews but drops to 5.04 on T13: Olympics. MCQ accuracy (Tables A8–A10) shows similar variation: Qwen3-Omni achieves 98.0% on T2 but only 82.4% on T7: Transportation.

Temporal hallucination in open-source models. Temporal localization (Tables A11–A13) reveals stark differences between models. Gemini maintains consistent grounding (MAE: 7.8–23.5s, R@0.5: 15.9–33.5%), while open-source models exhibit systematic temporal reference frame hallucination. Despite explicit prompting with absolute timestamps, most open-source models treat each 3-minute segment as starting at 0s. For example, UniMoE-2.0 achieves MAE of 1049.4–1532.0s on T1, T3, and T5 despite reasonable rationale scores (2.00–2.22), indicating models understand *what* happens but fail to ground *when* in absolute video time.

Model hierarchy. Results show clear performance tiers: Gemini (MAE: 7.8–23.5s), Qwen3-Omni (38.5–95.7s), VITA 1.5 (44.6–209.0s), and UniMoE-2.0/MiniCPM-o-2.6/VideoLLaMA2 (often 300–1500s). This exposes a fundamental limitation: most open-source models lack mechanisms to maintain temporal coherence across segments, treating each chunk

independently rather than as part of a continuous timeline.

Rationale-accuracy disconnect. High rationale scores do not guarantee temporal accuracy. VITA 1.5 achieves rationale scores of 3.37–4.45 but R@0.5 of 0.0–2.3% (MAE: 44.6–209.0s). UniMoE-2.0 and MiniCPM-o-2.6 similarly produce coherent explanations (scores 1.74–4.10) while exhibiting severe localization errors (MAE >1000s on multiple topics).

Professional vs. dynamic scenes. Models consistently perform better on structured interactions (T1: Patient-Doctor, T2: Job Interviews, T3: Parent-Teacher) than dynamic scenarios (T6: Emergency, T7: Transportation, T13: Olympics). Even Gemini’s MAE increases from 7.8–9.4s on structured topics to 13.4–23.5s on dynamic ones, though it remains substantially better than open-source alternatives.

G.2. Task 1: Video Summarization Per-Topic

Table A5. Task 1: Detailed Summarization Performance of MLLMs on Topics 1–4. Judge Score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), and Sim: Similarity (0–1) shown for detailed summaries. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic.

Model	T1: Patient-Dr.			T2: Job Int.			T3: Parent-Tch.			T4: Customer		
	Score	RG-L	Sim	Score	RG-L	Sim	Score	RG-L	Sim	Score	RG-L	Sim
Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	8.12	29.7	0.86	8.33	26.5	0.82	7.94	27.6	0.82	7.67	29.1	0.81
Qwen3-Omni	<u>7.38</u>	<u>24.6</u>	<u>0.78</u>	<u>7.14</u>	<u>25.5</u>	<u>0.76</u>	<u>6.72</u>	<u>22.2</u>	<u>0.74</u>	<u>6.13</u>	<u>25.6</u>	<u>0.74</u>
UniMoE-2.0	6.12	23.2	0.76	6.76	21.0	0.75	5.72	20.1	0.73	4.33	20.6	0.69
MiniCPM-o-2.6	4.94	15.8	0.70	4.19	15.5	0.59	4.28	13.8	0.60	3.20	14.7	0.59
VITA 1.5	4.44	18.3	0.63	3.71	17.2	0.53	4.22	16.1	0.54	1.73	17.2	0.51
VideoLLaMA2	2.31	13.6	0.49	2.19	11.9	0.43	2.28	11.9	0.38	1.27	12.3	0.43

Table A6. Task 1: Detailed Summarization Performance of MLLMs on Topics 5–8. Judge Score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), and Sim: Similarity (0–1) shown for detailed summaries. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic.

Model	T5: Courtroom			T6: Emergency			T7: Transport			T8: Workplace		
	Score	RG-L	Sim									
Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	6.54	25.1	0.79	6.25	27.6	0.77	7.43	28.1	0.85	7.00	26.7	0.83
Qwen3-Omni	<u>6.00</u>	<u>22.8</u>	<u>0.70</u>	<u>5.10</u>	<u>22.8</u>	<u>0.69</u>	4.86	<u>21.2</u>	<u>0.70</u>	<u>6.08</u>	<u>20.8</u>	<u>0.72</u>
UniMoE-2.0	4.08	21.1	0.67	3.90	20.4	0.64	3.29	19.5	0.69	<u>4.75</u>	19.2	0.69
MiniCPM-o-2.6	3.15	14.2	0.49	3.35	16.0	0.58	2.21	14.2	0.52	3.17	13.4	0.51
VITA 1.5	1.77	14.5	0.41	2.70	16.8	0.52	2.00	15.6	0.53	2.50	14.2	0.43
VideoLLaMA2	0.85	11.7	0.27	1.65	15.4	0.46	1.00	13.6	0.45	1.17	11.0	0.31

Table A7. Task 1: Detailed Summarization Performance of MLLMs on Topics 9–13. Score: Judge Score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), and Sim: Similarity (0–1) shown for detailed summaries. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic.

Model	T9: Housing			T10: Restaurant			T11: Mental Hlth			T12: Town Halls			T13: Olympics		
	Score	RG-L	Sim	Score	RG-L	Sim	Score	RG-L	Sim	Score	RG-L	Sim	Score	RG-L	Sim
Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	6.58	27.7	0.79	5.91	27.1	0.79	8.08	28.4	0.83	7.00	26.0	0.79	5.04	23.7	0.82
Qwen3-Omni	<u>4.58</u>	<u>23.0</u>	<u>0.67</u>	<u>5.00</u>	<u>23.2</u>	<u>0.72</u>	<u>7.23</u>	<u>26.3</u>	0.77	<u>4.72</u>	18.8	0.60	<u>3.39</u>	<u>19.2</u>	0.67
UniMoE-2.0	4.38	22.0	0.67	4.91	19.8	0.67	6.69	25.2	<u>0.79</u>	4.33	<u>19.8</u>	<u>0.65</u>	1.96	18.7	<u>0.70</u>
MiniCPM-o-2.6	2.88	14.9	0.50	3.13	15.3	0.60	4.46	15.6	0.63	2.06	11.7	0.39	2.43	16.5	0.63
VITA 1.5	2.58	17.0	0.43	2.26	17.2	0.46	3.69	17.6	0.55	2.28	14.1	0.34	2.09	16.6	0.50
VideoLLaMA2	1.50	14.1	0.35	1.70	13.8	0.42	2.08	13.3	0.42	0.83	9.8	0.18	1.13	12.9	0.39

G.3. Task 2: Multiple-Choice Questions Per-Topic

Table A8. **Task 2: MCQ Performance of MLLMs on Topics 1–4.** Acc.: Accuracy (%), Score: Rationale Judge Score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), and Sim: Similarity (0–1) shown. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic.

Model	T1: Patient-Dr.				T2: Job Int.				T3: Parent-Tch.				T4: Customer			
	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim
Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	99.0	9.82	42.6	0.82	<u>97.0</u>	9.64	40.0	0.80	98.7	9.63	38.9	0.80	94.9	9.13	31.9	0.78
Qwen3-Omni	<u>94.1</u>	<u>9.42</u>	<u>40.0</u>	<u>0.79</u>	98.0	<u>9.57</u>	<u>37.6</u>	<u>0.77</u>	<u>95.2</u>	<u>9.25</u>	<u>35.8</u>	<u>0.79</u>	<u>92.3</u>	<u>8.62</u>	<u>28.5</u>	<u>0.77</u>
UniMoE-2.0	92.2	8.97	29.6	0.76	94.0	9.21	28.4	0.73	92.6	8.92	27.7	0.75	76.9	7.03	26.7	0.74
MiniCPM-o-2.6	92.2	8.55	27.0	0.74	95.0	8.94	25.8	0.72	92.6	8.52	25.3	0.73	84.6	7.62	24.7	0.73
VITA 1.5	80.4	7.60	26.7	0.71	92.0	8.86	26.8	0.70	89.6	8.42	25.8	0.72	74.4	6.92	25.7	0.73
VideoLLaMA2	56.9	5.52	21.5	0.61	64.0	6.18	21.1	0.61	61.7	5.51	19.3	0.58	59.0	5.54	18.6	0.60

Table A9. **Task 2: MCQ Performance of MLLMs on Topics 5–8.** Acc.: Accuracy (%), Score: Rationale Judge Score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), and Sim: Similarity (0–1) shown. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic.

Model	T5: Courtroom				T6: Emergency				T7: Transport				T8: Workplace			
	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim												
Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	<u>96.5</u>	9.28	39.6	0.80	95.4	8.99	32.0	0.79	96.1	9.29	34.7	0.80	94.0	<u>9.45</u>	37.1	0.79
Qwen3-Omni	98.3	<u>9.28</u>	<u>36.8</u>	<u>0.79</u>	<u>87.4</u>	<u>8.39</u>	<u>28.6</u>	<u>0.76</u>	82.4	<u>7.73</u>	<u>26.6</u>	<u>0.74</u>	100.0	9.57	<u>36.7</u>	<u>0.78</u>
UniMoE-2.0	92.2	8.53	27.3	0.74	85.1	7.53	24.0	0.69	<u>88.2</u>	7.51	24.2	0.70	91.0	8.70	25.8	0.73
MiniCPM-o-2.6	87.0	8.37	25.7	0.73	85.1	7.24	23.7	0.72	82.4	7.33	22.6	0.71	<u>95.5</u>	8.61	23.6	0.76
VITA 1.5	87.0	7.97	26.1	0.71	79.3	7.61	25.2	0.71	84.3	7.33	24.0	0.72	85.1	8.45	24.8	0.73
VideoLLaMA2	51.3	4.16	18.3	0.54	55.2	4.94	17.5	0.55	49.0	5.24	18.3	0.59	53.7	5.16	19.4	0.60

Table A10. **Task 2: MCQ Performance of MLLMs on Topics 9–13.** Acc.: Accuracy (%), Score: Rationale Judge Score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), and Sim: Similarity (0–1) shown. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic.

Model	T9: Housing				T10: Restaurant				T11: Mental Hlth				T12: Town Halls				T13: Olympics			
	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim
Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]	95.3	9.29	38.6	0.80	97.8	9.33	36.3	0.82	<u>98.5</u>	9.63	36.3	<u>0.79</u>	96.8	9.49	40.2	0.81	92.8	8.96	31.8	0.82
Qwen3-Omni	<u>93.8</u>	<u>8.79</u>	<u>36.8</u>	<u>0.78</u>	<u>94.4</u>	<u>8.77</u>	<u>34.2</u>	<u>0.79</u>	100.0	<u>9.57</u>	<u>34.3</u>	0.80	<u>94.2</u>	<u>9.13</u>	<u>36.1</u>	<u>0.78</u>	<u>87.0</u>	<u>7.39</u>	<u>27.0</u>	<u>0.77</u>
UniMoE-2.0	85.3	7.82	27.5	0.73	80.0	7.50	27.5	0.75	93.8	8.71	24.6	0.73	93.7	8.53	28.4	0.73	81.2	6.64	22.3	0.69
MiniCPM-o-2.6	80.6	7.26	24.3	0.70	82.4	7.79	24.8	0.74	89.2	8.48	23.2	0.74	92.1	8.25	24.3	0.71	78.3	7.13	22.3	0.73
VITA 1.5	76.0	7.03	25.7	0.68	64.4	6.49	24.4	0.69	87.7	8.54	24.0	0.74	84.7	8.02	25.0	0.70	75.4	7.10	23.5	0.72
VideoLLaMA2	51.9	4.38	19.4	0.56	45.6	4.50	17.8	0.55	50.8	4.83	16.5	0.52	58.2	5.59	20.5	0.59	49.3	4.94	18.0	0.61

G.4. Task 3: Temporal Localization Per-Topic

Table A11. Task 3: Temporal Localization Performance of MLLMs on Topics 1–4. mIoU (%), R@0.5 (%), MAE (seconds), and Score: Rationale Judge Score (0–10) shown. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic. ↓ indicates lower is better.

Model	T1: Patient-Dr.				T2: Job Int.				T3: Parent-Tch.				T4: Customer			
	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score
Gemini 3.0 Pro†	20.2	18.6	9.2	5.01	32.1	31.0	8.9	5.47	22.7	21.0	12.5	5.12	30.1	31.9	13.4	5.82
Qwen3-Omni	<u>5.0</u>	<u>4.5</u>	<u>57.4</u>	<u>2.73</u>	<u>6.3</u>	<u>5.5</u>	<u>58.3</u>	<u>2.78</u>	<u>3.1</u>	<u>1.5</u>	<u>49.9</u>	<u>2.72</u>	<u>3.7</u>	<u>3.4</u>	<u>62.7</u>	<u>2.40</u>
UniMoE-2.0	2.0	1.9	1049.4	2.05	2.5	1.2	618.8	2.17	0.9	1.0	1423.0	2.22	3.1	0.9	315.8	1.98
MiniCPM-o-2.6	1.4	0.4	657.9	3.37	3.3	1.6	372.0	3.50	2.1	<u>1.5</u>	1041.5	3.41	2.1	0.9	123.3	<u>4.58</u>
VITA 1.5	3.5	3.8	170.1	<u>3.77</u>	2.6	1.2	122.2	<u>3.79</u>	2.3	1.3	176.2	<u>3.58</u>	1.2	0.9	86.2	4.04
VideoLLaMA2	4.0	1.1	357.0	2.05	4.2	0.4	219.2	<u>2.05</u>	<u>3.1</u>	0.2	510.7	2.19	<u>4.7</u>	0.0	126.4	2.00

Table A12. Task 3: Temporal Localization Performance of MLLMs on Topics 5–8. mIoU (%), R@0.5 (%), MAE (seconds), and Score: Rationale Judge Score (0–10) shown. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic. ↓ indicates lower is better.

Model	T5: Courtroom				T6: Emergency				T7: Transport				T8: Workplace			
	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score												
Gemini 3.0 Pro†	32.7	33.5	15.1	5.38	20.0	17.8	14.1	5.44	27.0	22.6	7.8	6.09	28.8	29.6	10.2	5.31
Qwen3-Omni	<u>4.0</u>	<u>2.9</u>	<u>38.5</u>	<u>2.59</u>	<u>3.0</u>	<u>2.4</u>	<u>42.3</u>	<u>2.46</u>	1.4	0.0	<u>44.8</u>	<u>2.57</u>	4.1	3.2	<u>59.0</u>	2.50
UniMoE-2.0	1.1	0.6	1532.0	2.00	1.4	0.4	477.4	2.03	1.6	<u>1.0</u>	550.3	2.64	4.8	<u>3.3</u>	391.5	1.94
MiniCPM-o-2.6	2.3	1.5	652.0	3.28	1.1	0.0	238.1	4.10	0.3	0.0	263.0	3.91	1.6	0.7	302.7	3.29
VITA 1.5	1.8	1.5	128.4	<u>4.08</u>	0.7	0.0	63.9	<u>4.45</u>	0.6	0.0	137.7	<u>4.31</u>	1.5	0.0	166.2	<u>3.59</u>
VideoLLaMA2	<u>3.2</u>	0.3	480.8	2.25	1.8	0.4	215.6	2.52	<u>3.4</u>	0.0	179.7	3.40	<u>4.9</u>	1.3	176.0	2.33

Table A13. Task 3: Temporal Localization Performance of MLLMs on Topics 9–13. mIoU (%), R@0.5 (%), MAE (seconds), and Score: Rationale Judge Score (0–10) shown. **Bold** = best, underline = second-best per topic. ↓ indicates lower is better.

Model	T9: Housing				T10: Restaurant				T11: Mental Hlth				T12: Town Halls				T13: Olympics			
	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score	mIoU	R@0.5	MAE↓	Score
Gemini 3.0 Pro†	29.5	27.6	8.5	5.16	27.7	26.6	9.4	5.52	29.5	29.6	9.4	5.45	20.5	15.9	23.5	5.07	25.2	24.8	13.6	5.11
Qwen3-Omni	3.3	<u>3.1</u>	73.9	2.20	<u>5.8</u>	<u>4.3</u>	<u>82.7</u>	2.65	3.2	<u>2.6</u>	67.1	2.66	<u>4.2</u>	<u>3.0</u>	<u>95.7</u>	2.97	1.3	0.0	<u>47.2</u>	2.29
UniMoE-2.0	1.3	0.8	401.3	2.08	2.2	0.5	429.0	2.45	0.9	0.7	429.7	1.74	0.4	0.2	1111.6	2.18	1.3	1.2	185.3	1.95
MiniCPM-o-2.6	2.2	1.3	170.9	3.42	1.8	0.5	201.9	3.97	2.8	0.7	208.2	3.68	2.2	0.5	469.7	3.62	0.3	0.0	71.4	3.38
VITA 1.5	2.4	1.6	<u>52.5</u>	<u>4.36</u>	1.7	0.5	96.9	<u>4.39</u>	1.1	0.7	<u>55.6</u>	<u>3.37</u>	2.3	1.3	209.0	<u>3.39</u>	1.9	<u>2.3</u>	44.6	<u>3.66</u>
VideoLLaMA2	<u>3.6</u>	0.5	134.2	2.37	3.1	0.0	129.4	2.10	<u>3.2</u>	0.0	168.3	1.83	3.2	0.2	253.1	1.77	<u>3.0</u>	1.1	98.3	2.01

H. Error Taxonomy Analysis

To better understand failure modes in Task 3 (Temporal Localization), we categorize each prediction into a small set of error types. In this task, models are given absolute segment boundaries and are required to output absolute timestamps within the provided segment. Ground-truth timestamps are obtained by converting segment-relative annotations to absolute video time by adding the segment start offset.

Notation. Let the ground-truth interval be $G = [s_{gt}, e_{gt}]$ and the predicted interval be $P = [s_{pred}, e_{pred}]$, both in seconds. We use the same IoU and MAE definitions as in the main evaluation.

H.1. Category assignment rules

Each prediction is assigned to exactly one category using the following rules (evaluated in order). We use two fixed thresholds: a reference-frame tolerance $\tau_{relabs} = 10s$ and a timing-shift tolerance $\tau_{shift} = 5s$.

Relative-to-absolute mismatch captures cases where the model outputs timestamps as if time “starts at 0” at the beginning of the segment (i.e., segment-relative), even though the task requires absolute video time. We detect this by shifting the prediction by the segment start time: $P' = [s_{pred} + S, e_{pred} + S]$, where S is the segment start. If this shifted interval P' is close to the ground truth (within $\tau_{relabs} = 10s$) while the original P is not, we label the prediction as a relative-to-absolute mismatch.

Hallucination covers violations of output validity or prompt constraints: (i) malformed intervals (non-numeric timestamps or $e_{pred} \leq s_{pred}$), (ii) timestamps outside the provided segment bounds, or (iii) timestamps outside the full video duration

when available. This category also includes extreme “teleport” errors where the predicted interval is far from the provided segment window.

Timing shift (Too Early / Too Late) is assigned when overlap with the ground truth is negligible ($\text{IoU}(P, G) < 0.1$) and the prediction is clearly before or after the ground truth by more than τ_{shift} seconds: *Too Early* if $e_{\text{pred}} < s_{\text{gt}} - \tau_{\text{shift}}$; *Too Late* if $s_{\text{pred}} > e_{\text{gt}} + \tau_{\text{shift}}$.

Wrong event, right time is a semantic proxy: we assign it when temporal overlap is high ($\text{IoU}(P, G) > 0.5$) but the rationale is judged poor (LLM-judge score < 5), suggesting the model localized a different event occurring at a similar time.

Other includes all remaining errors not covered above.

H.2. Key Observations

Figure A9 provides qualitative examples of UniMoE-2.0 predictions and Gemini 3.0 Pro. Table A14 shows clear, model-dependent failure patterns. Uni-MoE-2.0 exhibits a large fraction of relative-to-absolute mismatches (39.4%), indicating that reference-frame confusion is a primary source of error for this model. MiniCPM-o-2.6 also shows substantial hallucination (26.8%) and a strong tendency toward late timing shifts (37.5%), suggesting frequent violations of segment constraints and delayed localization. By contrast, Qwen3-Omni and VITA-1.5 are dominated by timing shifts (Too Early + Too Late = 67.4% and 74.6%, respectively), consistent with models often selecting the correct neighborhood but misplacing the interval. Gemini 3.0 Pro has very low hallucination and reference-frame errors, but a large residual *Other* bucket (81.5%), indicating that most of its mistakes do not follow a single dominant structural pattern under this taxonomy. VideoLLaMA2 shows a more balanced profile, with moderate reference-frame errors (10.4%) and hallucination (10.0%), and the remainder largely falling into *Other* (50.2%).

Table A14. **Error taxonomy distribution (%) for Task 3 temporal localization.** Error breakdown of MLLMs predictions on all dataset. Hallucination aggregates invalid outputs, out-of-bounds timestamps, and extreme “teleport” errors. Each prediction is assigned to exactly one category.

Model	Relative–Absolute	Hallucination	Too Early	Too Late	Wrong Event / Right Time	Other
Gemini 3.0 Pro	0.2	0.4	5.6	9.2	3.1	81.5
Qwen3-Omni	0.5	7.0	30.5	36.9	1.3	23.8
Uni-MoE-2.0	39.4	27.1	13.0	9.6	0.7	10.1
VideoLLaMA2	10.4	10.0	17.6	11.6	0.3	50.2
MiniCPM-o-2.6	7.3	26.8	14.8	37.5	0.6	12.9
VITA-1.5	0.8	7.7	38.0	36.6	0.5	16.4

I. Detailed Results Across Demographic Groups

Tables A15–A18 report performance stratified by race, gender, and age. Demographic disparities are systematic: the same groups consistently underperform across models and tasks, indicating persistent robustness gaps.

Race disparities. Models most consistently underperform on Black participants. In summarization, Gemini drops from 7.05 (Asian) to 6.02 (Black; -1.03), and Qwen from 5.95 (Arab) to 4.39 (Black; -1.56). Indigenous participants show inconsistent treatment: some models remain competitive, while others degrade sharply (Qwen: 4.13, VITA: 1.65), suggesting limited coverage of Indigenous speech patterns in training corpora.

Gender disparities. Female-participant videos consistently yield higher performance across all models and tasks. Female advantages in summarization range from $+0.17$ to $+0.66$ across models. The uniform directionality suggests systematic differences in processing male vs. female voices and interaction styles.

Age disparities. Models favor older speakers. For summarization, the 40+ group outperforms 18–24 (Gemini: 6.91 vs. 6.28), consistent with training data skewed toward formal, professional contexts aligned with older-participant scenarios.

Temporal localization failures. Temporal localization exhibits the most severe disparities. For Indigenous participants, open-source models collapse to 0.0% R@0.5 while Gemini achieves 40.9%, indicating binary failure where systems fail to register critical temporal grounding cues. This contrasts with Black participants, where performance degrades but does not completely collapse (Gemini: 19.5% R@0.5), implying different underlying error mechanisms across subgroups.

Figure A9. Qualitative examples of temporal localization errors. Three common error types are illustrated: **Too Early** (top)—predictions preceding the ground truth event; **Relative-to-Absolute mismatch** (middle)—model outputs segment-relative rather than absolute timestamps; **Too Late** (bottom)—predictions following the ground truth event. Each example shows the question, ground truth timestamps, and predictions from UniMoE-2.0 and Gemini-3.0-Pro.

Implications. These disparities likely reflect upstream biases in pre-training corpora rather than annotation artifacts. Demographic slice sizes are uneven and can inflate variance for smaller groups. Generation-oriented summarization shows relative stability, while reasoning-heavy MCQ and especially temporal localization expose larger robustness failures across demographic groups.

Table A15. Performance of MLLMs on the summarization task across demographics. Results are on all dataset. Score: Judge score (0–10), ROUGE-L (%), and Sim: similarity (0–1). **Bold** = best, **highlighted** = worst within each demographic group (Race/Gender/Age) per column.

Group	Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]			Qwen3-Omni			UniMoE-2.0			MiniCPM-o-2.6			VITA 1.5			VideoLLaMA2		
	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim	Score	ROUGE-L	Sim
<i>Race</i>																		
Arab	6.90	27.8	0.811	5.95	22.2	0.695	5.00	21.9	0.706	3.57	14.1	0.576	2.76	16.4	0.465	1.00	11.5	0.289
Indigenous	6.70	24.3	0.853	4.13	19.0	0.745	4.35	18.9	0.749	3.61	14.6	0.689	1.65	15.2	0.440	1.04	8.9	0.227
Asian	7.05	27.9	0.818	5.71	23.2	0.740	4.62	20.2	0.695	3.26	14.5	0.579	2.65	15.8	0.488	1.63	13.0	0.412
White	6.68	25.9	0.809	5.28	21.6	0.701	4.29	20.2	0.699	3.26	14.7	0.572	2.50	16.0	0.476	1.45	12.7	0.367
Hispanic	6.41	26.3	0.809	4.99	21.8	0.704	3.70	20.2	0.691	3.04	15.0	0.558	2.21	15.1	0.466	1.23	12.6	0.352
Black	6.02	25.2	0.806	4.39	20.8	0.663	3.45	19.0	0.683	2.92	14.9	0.559	2.31	15.7	0.438	1.38	13.1	0.363
<i>Gender</i>																		
Male	6.36	25.8	0.809	4.97	21.4	0.698	3.93	19.8	0.690	2.98	14.6	0.567	2.31	15.8	0.470	1.36	12.8	0.370
Female	7.02	26.9	0.816	5.47	22.2	0.713	4.55	20.3	0.707	3.53	14.8	0.583	2.65	15.9	0.467	1.53	12.4	0.361
<i>Age</i>																		
18–24	6.28	25.4	0.818	4.93	21.5	0.713	4.02	20.0	0.710	3.30	15.3	0.623	2.41	16.7	0.493	1.38	12.5	0.387
25–39	6.52	26.2	0.811	5.01	21.5	0.703	4.01	19.7	0.689	3.14	14.7	0.570	2.45	15.7	0.466	1.50	12.8	0.377
40+	6.91	26.7	0.809	5.47	22.1	0.700	4.45	20.5	0.699	3.21	14.4	0.552	2.47	15.5	0.461	1.36	12.6	0.345

SONIC-O1: A Real-World Benchmark for Evaluating Multimodal Large Language Models

Table A16. Performance of MLLMs on the MCQ task across demographics. Results on all dataset. Acc.: Accuracy (%), and rationale quality (Score: Judge score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), Sim: similarity (0–1)). **Bold** = best, **highlighted** = worst within each demographic group per column.

Group	Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]				Qwen3-Omni				UniMoE-2.0				MiniCPM-o-2.6				VITA 1.5				VideoLLaMA2			
	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim	Acc.	Score	RG-L	Sim
<i>Race</i>																								
Arab	98.4	9.44	37.4	0.802	96.9	9.09	35.1	0.790	95.3	8.95	27.9	0.753	92.7	8.21	24.4	0.738	93.2	8.47	25.5	0.729	67.0	5.59	19.4	0.561
Indigenous	94.3	9.03	31.8	0.825	77.1	6.86	29.4	0.771	80.0	6.74	20.3	0.631	82.9	7.09	22.6	0.758	62.9	6.17	24.0	0.726	65.7	6.17	19.5	0.597
Asian	97.8	9.43	37.7	0.807	96.1	9.12	34.2	0.781	89.2	7.90	26.4	0.723	88.7	8.28	24.2	0.729	84.6	7.83	24.8	0.705	57.9	5.21	19.0	0.564
White	96.9	9.41	37.6	0.802	93.3	8.90	34.3	0.779	88.9	8.13	26.3	0.723	87.5	8.08	24.4	0.729	82.0	7.81	24.8	0.712	55.1	5.12	18.6	0.576
Hispanic	95.8	9.19	35.7	0.796	92.8	8.53	31.7	0.772	86.4	7.79	27.0	0.734	82.2	7.39	23.8	0.723	79.9	7.46	25.0	0.720	51.5	4.64	18.5	0.581
Black	96.4	9.27	36.6	0.805	92.0	8.66	32.7	0.784	87.4	7.84	25.9	0.723	86.3	7.66	23.3	0.723	82.2	7.70	24.6	0.715	55.0	5.02	19.0	0.584
<i>Gender</i>																								
Male	96.4	9.29	36.8	0.804	93.5	8.77	33.4	0.779	88.0	7.93	26.2	0.720	86.1	7.89	23.9	0.728	81.6	7.71	24.7	0.713	52.6	4.91	18.7	0.575
Female	97.7	9.48	37.6	0.801	93.4	8.93	34.1	0.781	89.3	8.21	26.6	0.733	88.4	8.05	24.3	0.729	83.8	7.87	24.9	0.714	60.0	5.36	19.0	0.578
<i>Age</i>																								
18–24	97.4	9.31	34.3	0.802	91.5	8.36	30.0	0.773	82.4	7.33	23.2	0.690	83.6	7.67	22.9	0.730	82.1	7.80	24.1	0.723	54.8	5.06	17.4	0.565
25–39	95.6	9.27	36.4	0.802	92.7	8.76	33.4	0.780	87.5	7.90	26.2	0.724	86.7	7.89	23.9	0.727	81.4	7.67	24.7	0.712	55.6	5.09	18.7	0.574
40+	98.0	9.48	38.4	0.804	94.6	9.01	34.9	0.781	91.0	8.33	27.2	0.734	88.2	8.08	24.5	0.728	83.7	7.87	25.1	0.712	56.4	5.12	19.2	0.579

Table A17. Performance of MLLMs on the temporal localization task across demographics (Models 1–3). Results on all dataset. mIoU (%), R@0.3/R@0.5 (%), and rationale quality (Score: Judge score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), Sim: similarity (0–1)). **Bold** = best, **highlighted** = worst within each demographic group per column.

Group	Gemini 3.0 Pro [†]						Qwen3-Omni						UniMoE-2.0						
	mIoU	R@0.3	R@0.5	Score	RG-L	Sim	mIoU	R@0.3	R@0.5	Score	RG-L	Sim	mIoU	R@0.3	R@0.5	Score	RG-L	Sim	
<i>Race</i>																			
Arab	23.4	32.6	21.1	5.23	26.9	0.638	2.3	2.9	1.6	2.59	27.0	0.686	0.7	0.2	0.2	2.33	22.6	0.530	
Indigenous	36.7	55.7	40.9	6.41	28.0	0.694	4.0	8.1	0.0	2.48	27.5	0.677	1.2	1.3	1.3	2.51	28.3	0.594	
Asian	31.3	46.6	30.7	5.69	27.6	0.658	4.5	6.1	2.9	2.67	27.6	0.690	1.6	1.8	0.6	2.26	22.8	0.521	
White	24.4	35.3	23.0	5.22	28.0	0.666	3.6	5.2	2.6	2.62	27.7	0.695	1.6	2.0	1.2	2.10	23.9	0.557	
Hispanic	25.1	36.6	23.8	5.19	27.6	0.669	3.4	5.4	2.3	2.58	27.1	0.684	0.7	0.8	0.1	2.08	23.7	0.566	
Black	22.4	33.5	19.5	5.20	28.4	0.675	3.3	4.8	1.8	2.60	28.0	0.696	0.9	0.8	0.6	2.15	24.4	0.566	
<i>Gender</i>																			
Male	25.1	37.1	23.5	5.21	27.8	0.665	3.7	5.3	2.6	2.59	27.8	0.695	1.5	1.7	0.9	2.14	23.9	0.556	
Female	25.7	37.0	24.2	5.42	28.0	0.666	3.5	5.1	2.1	2.66	27.5	0.689	1.2	1.2	0.7	2.16	23.6	0.548	
<i>Age</i>																			
18–24	27.9	42.8	27.3	5.64	29.4	0.696	3.9	6.5	2.4	2.57	29.7	0.712	1.8	1.8	1.2	2.34	26.5	0.589	
25–39	26.1	38.2	25.2	5.35	27.7	0.668	3.4	4.7	2.5	2.51	27.5	0.694	1.7	2.1	1.2	2.15	23.8	0.555	
40+	24.2	34.9	21.9	5.20	27.8	0.658	3.7	5.4	2.3	2.72	27.4	0.687	0.9	0.9	0.4	2.11	23.3	0.544	

Table A18. Performance of MLLMs on the temporal localization task across demographics (Models 4–6). Results on all dataset. mIoU (%), R@0.3/R@0.5 (%), and rationale quality (Score: Judge score (0–10), RG-L: ROUGE-L (%), Sim: similarity (0–1)). **Bold** = best, **highlighted** = worst within each demographic group per column.

Group	MiniCPM-o-2.6						VITA 1.5						VideoLLaMA2						
	mIoU	R@0.3	R@0.5	Score	RG-L	Sim	mIoU	R@0.3	R@0.5	Score	RG-L	Sim	mIoU	R@0.3	R@0.5	Score	RG-L	Sim	
<i>Race</i>																			
Arab	3.0	3.6	2.6	3.46	18.6	0.412	2.0	2.6	1.2	3.62	22.0	0.433	2.5	0.5	0.0	2.19	22.7	0.496	
Indigenous	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.23	21.1	0.484	1.2	1.3	1.3	4.56	23.9	0.501	4.8	1.3	1.3	2.46	22.0	0.516	
Asian	2.1	3.0	0.8	3.60	18.1	0.377	2.3	3.5	1.4	4.03	20.8	0.403	3.8	1.4	0.4	1.99	22.9	0.512	
White	2.0	2.5	0.9	3.56	19.3	0.405	1.9	2.9	1.4	3.88	22.0	0.434	3.4	1.8	0.5	2.14	22.2	0.493	
Hispanic	1.9	2.5	0.2	3.65	18.6	0.399	1.7	3.0	0.8	3.70	21.8	0.431	3.0	1.5	0.0	2.27	21.3	0.494	
Black	2.1	2.7	0.3	3.77	19.4	0.416	2.3	4.0	1.4	4.08	22.1	0.445	2.8	1.1	0.3	2.02	23.2	0.525	
<i>Gender</i>																			
Male	1.9	2.5	0.7	3.62	19.3	0.405	1.9	3.0	1.2	3.90	21.9	0.432	3.3	1.5	0.4	2.06	22.6	0.507	
Female	2.3	2.9	0.9	3.60	18.7	0.400	2.2	3.4	1.4	3.93	21.6	0.429	3.4	1.5	0.4	2.19	22.3	0.497	
<i>Age</i>																			
18–24	2.2	3.6	1.1	3.97	21.0	0.432	1.6	2.0	1.1	4.40	23.3	0.455	3.1	0.8	0.3	2.29	24.7	0.545	
25–39	1.9	2.4	0.7	3.65	18.8	0.404	2.0	3.2	1.2	3.96	21.5	0.432	3.2	1.2	0.3	2.15	22.4	0.503	
40+	2.2	2.7	0.8	3.52	18.9	0.396	2.2	3.3	1.5	3.79	21.8	0.426	3.4	1.9	0.4	2.05	22.1	0.494	

Table A19. **Emotional language analysis.** Analysis of MLLM empathic summary outputs on the all dataset (Task 1: summarization) using LIWC-22 categories. **Bold** denotes best performance, underline denotes second-best.

Model	Prosocial (%)	Affiliation (%)	Insight (%)	Total Emotion (%)	Neg. Emotion (%)	Tone (percentile)
Gemini 3.0 Pro	1.82	2.68	3.07	4.35	2.03	46.16
Qwen3-Omni	<u>1.97</u>	2.78	3.00	<u>3.88</u>	<u>1.39</u>	<u>56.99</u>
UniMoE-2.0	2.07	<u>2.69</u>	<u>3.39</u>	3.54	0.93	57.94
MiniCPM-o-2.6	1.06	1.42	<u>2.51</u>	1.41	0.38	46.10
VITA-1.5	1.60	2.08	3.51	2.65	0.59	55.45
VideoLLaMA2	0.62	0.93	2.16	2.02	0.49	49.83

J. Emotional Language Analysis

In Section 4.4, we discussed empathic capabilities of models. Table A19 reports the psycholinguistic profile of model empathic summaries across six LIWC-22 dimensions: **Prosocial** (helping or caring language such as "support", "help"), **Affiliation** (references to social connections like "friend", "together"), **Insight** (cognitive understanding words like "realize", "understand"), **Total Emotion** (any emotional vocabulary), **Negative Emotion** (distress-specific terms like "anxious", "worried"), and **Tone** (overall warmth and positivity on 0-100 percentile scale, where higher values indicate warmer, more informal language).

J.1. Key Observations

Divergent empathy strategies. Models adopt fundamentally different empathic approaches. Gemini prioritizes emotional validation (4.35% Total Emotion, 2.03% Negative Emotion) but maintains formal tone (46.16, below neutral 50th percentile). UniMoE-2.0 shows the opposite profile: highest Prosocial language (2.07%) and warmest Tone (57.94) but lower emotional intensity (3.54%, 0.93%). Qwen3-Omni falls between these extremes (1.97% Prosocial, 3.88% Emotion, 56.99 Tone), demonstrating balanced empathic expression.

Cognitive vs. affective empathy. VITA-1.5 achieves the highest Insight score (3.51%), reflecting strong cognitive perspective-taking, yet minimal emotional validation (0.59% Negative Emotion). This dissociation reveals that VITA 1.5 can articulate understanding of mental states but fails to express emotional responses, showing understanding without feeling.

Small model limitations. Smaller models (MiniCPM-o-2.6, VideoLLaMA2) show consistently weak empathic performance. VideoLLaMA2 produces only 0.62% Prosocial language and 2.02% Total Emotion with near-neutral Tone (49.83), reading as detached clinical descriptions. These results show that empathic modulation requires model scale since smaller models default to factual reporting without adapting linguistic style to emotional contexts.

Tone-emotion independence. Tone and emotional vocabulary do not correlate: Gemini’s high emotion (4.35%, 2.03%) pairs with low Tone (46.16), while UniMoE’s high Tone (57.94) pairs with lower emotion (3.54%, 0.93%). This pattern reveals that warmth and emotional validation are orthogonal dimensions. The optimal balance depends on context: medical consultations may benefit from Gemini’s approach (serious tone, high emotional validation), while customer service may favor UniMoE’s profile (warm tone, supportive language).

Implications. Current models lack nuanced empathic control. While commercial models demonstrate some capacity for empathic modulation when prompted, they adopt fixed strategies rather than adapting to situational demands. Future work should explore fine-grained empathy prompting that separately controls emotional validation, warmth, and perspective-taking; context-adaptive empathy that adjusts based on interaction type; and empathy-focused training objectives beyond standard language modeling.

Data Release and License

To support transparency and reproducibility, we release the full dataset alongside this preprint at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/vector-institute/sonic-o1>. All personally identifiable information (PII) was removed during preprocessing. The dataset is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license, which permits reuse, redistribution, and adaptation with appropriate attribution to the original authors. We also release the scripts used to process the data and reproduce the experiments in the same repository. The dataset page includes a persistent download link and detailed documentation (e.g., dataset structure, fields, and usage instructions).